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Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced

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Policy Brief

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<i>About RAISD</i>	
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<p><i>Forced displacement crises overcome societies and institutions all over the world. Pushed by the urgencies rather than events, solutions are frequently reactive, partial, and disregard some groups. The project 'Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced' (RAISD) aims at identifying highly Vulnerable Groups (VG) among these forcibly displaced people, analysing their specific needs, and finding suitable practices to address them. The concept of 'vulnerability context' considers the interplay between the features of these persons and their hosting communities, their interactions and experiences, and how different solutions for attention and inclusion affect them. As a result of this work, a methodology to carry out these studies will be developed. These goals are aligned with the call. They pursue characterizing these migrations and developing suitable aid strategies for them. The Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) frames the project. It proposes that all actors (including civil society) co-design actions, transversely integrates the gender perspective, and supports sustainability. Our research strategy will be based on methodological triangulation (i.e. the combined application of several methodologies). We will implement it through a specific participatory action research approach to fulfil the aim of undertaking advocacy-focused research, grounded in human rights and socio-ecological models. The team will work as a network of units in countries along migration routes. The units will promote the VG people' involvement, so they can speak with their own voices, gather information, and test practices. Work will rely on a tight integration of Social and Computer Sciences research. Automated learning and data mining will help to provide evidence-based recommendations, reducing a priori biases. A software tool will support collaboration, continuing previous H2020- funded RRI work.</i></p>	

The sole responsibility of this publication lies with the author.

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Glossary

AB	Advisory Board
ARU	Action Research Unit
CEAR	Spanish Commission for Refugee Aid
EQPR	European Qualifications Passport for Refugees
EU	European Union
FD	Forcibly Displaced
FDP	Forcibly Displaced People / Person
GBV	Gender-Based Violence
HES code	Hayat Eve Siğar – (Life Fits into Home)
HVG	Highly Vulnerable Group
ILO	International Labour Organisation
LGBTQI+	Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Trans, Queer, Intersex and Plus
LIU	Lebanese International University
MoPH	(Lebanese) Ministry of Social Affairs and the Ministry of Public Health
MOSA	(Lebanese) Ministry of Social Affairs
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
PR	Policy Recommendations
RAISD	Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced
SGBV	Sexual and Gender-Based Violence
UAM	UnAccompanied Minor
UNHCR	United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees
UN	United Nations
VG	Vulnerable Group

Executive Summary

As indicated in the Grant Agreement, the aim of this deliverable is “summarising the main results and findings of the project for stakeholders”. With this objective, the different partners of the consortium, Action Research Unit (ARU) members and other experts representing the quintuple helix of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) - policymakers, researchers, educators, businesses, Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs) and Forcibly Displaced People (FDP) themselves- have collected policy recommendations related to the attention and inclusion of Vulnerable Groups (VGs) among the FDP throughout the several phases of the project. This is a valuable contribution, as it tackles this issue from all the main important perspectives involved, something innovative in the research about this topic that allows us to acquire a deeper understanding.

Considering all the work of RAISD project since its beginning in February 2019 -the state of the art, the results of all ARU meetings, the comments of Advisory Board (AB) members, interviews with experts and Highly VGs (HVGs) among the FDP, and other focus groups- numerous experts have reflected on the current situation of each country of RAISD consortium related to vulnerabilities in the different socio-ecological levels, issues of diversity, and good practices for the attention and inclusion of FDP, in order to develop this Policy Brief.

In this Policy brief, vulnerability refers to a situation determined by both contextual conditions and individual features and capabilities. Vulnerability not only indicates one's exposure to potential harms but refers to the reduced capacity to cope with the harms as well. Even though vulnerability is a universal human condition, the level of vulnerability tends to change according to contextual and situational factors. In this way, the concept of vulnerability should be redefined in the legislation as well as in the public discourse. The notion of vulnerability needs to be seen as contextual and situational. The same person can be resilient in one context/situation and vulnerable in some other. For a practical implementation of the concept of vulnerability context, interested stakeholders can consult our “Guidelines for the identification of vulnerable contexts” (D4.2).

The analysis of micro, meso and macro levels of socio-ecological levels shows a big picture about the inclusion of VGs. It allows analysing the political will, successes and failures of European governments and institutions regarding these issues.

On the negative side, the lack of knowledge about vulnerability contexts does not allow them to protect those who suffer these conditions properly. Moreover, even when the groups are sufficiently defined and there is a formal commitment to safeguard their fundamental rights, in practice, the time and resources allocated to the inclusion of VGs among the FDP are not sufficient, because, in the end, these people cannot get out of their vulnerability most of the time. Thus, we are facing three relevant factors that determine social exclusion of VGs among the FDP: ignorance due to how vulnerability is defined, the absence of decisive political will, and the lack of resources.

On the positive side, by analysing those levels with VGs among FDP and the other stakeholders involved, we have detected key aspects that could be improved by implementing tailored actions considering each vulnerability context. Although some of these actions could require a change in policies, others are specific modifications on strategies and practices that are easier to implement.

The report also includes a section on “Issues of diversity”. It reflects on this intersectional perspective and how the vulnerabilities intersect and add up in human beings. This knowledge will enable stakeholders and representatives of the institutions to apply more complete and tailored solutions to this complex and multi-dimensional reality. It also calls for budgets to be increased, so that social care can be tailored to the profile of asylum seekers and their

specific needs. When defining the different VGs that apply for international protection, it is necessary to adopt an intersectional approach due to the different forms of oppression suffered, including the gender perspective.

Finally, the section about “Successful practices” gathers information about currently implemented actions with a distinctive positive impact on VGs among the FDP and their host communities. One interesting general finding here is that the actions of civil society and NGOs are often efficiently supplying what administrations do not achieve. Thus, the catalogue of policy recommendations derived from best practices and included in this policy brief, could be useful for stakeholders working in specific aspects of social inclusion as educational, labour, or housing factors in each vulnerability context. It could also inspire potential policy modifications.

1 Policy brief summarising the main results and findings of the project for stakeholders from Anadolu University (Turkey)

1.1 Vulnerability

1.1.1 On micro-level. Considerations about personal conditions and features

Individual factors:

Vulnerability in Turkey is observed intensely at every socio-ecological level. At the micro level, FDP are struggling with the traumas caused by forced migration. Although they may have escaped from the physical violence in their country of origin, they face many psychological problems such as foreignness, loneliness, homesickness, and exclusion in the process of getting used to the culture of the host country. FDP can access mental health services from government primary health units and NGOs. However, due to the lack of knowledge about the importance and necessity of mental health care these services are insufficient compared to the needs of FDP. Therefore, the quantity and quality of mental health services should be improved especially regarding refugees residing in rural areas. On the other hand, members of the LGBTQI+ community also need mental health support taking into consideration the challenges they face regarding war trauma, violence, economic conditions, and discriminative issues. Therefore, the services provided for FDP should also include the specific needs and challenges of the aforementioned disadvantaged social groups.

Many FDP lose their physical health in addition to their mental health during migration. This should be considered, and the staff should be informed and educated on how to communicate and support FDP who suffer extreme cases of physical and psychological violence.

Intra-family factors:

The majority of FDP in Turkey are women and girls, and these individuals have limited their communication due to the patriarchal social structure. Their anxiety of being in a new country and the fact that they carry out domestic service for which there is no payment, makes that the man, who is accepted as the "head" of the household, controls the social lives of women and girls. This situation mostly results in domestic violence because women and girls who cannot exist as individuals in the society are at the mercy of the decision mechanisms within the family. This puts them in a very fragile position. In this case, economic independence is really important for refugee women. The government should increase the number of vocational training courses provided for women and girls. Also, there should be helplines to assist specifically forcibly displaced women facing gender-based violence. In this line also, divorce processes are easier for men, but more difficult for women. First, it is very difficult for a woman who does not have economic freedom to get custody of the child. For this reason, custody of the child is usually given to the father. In addition, many men threaten their ex-spouse and even inflict violence on their ex-wife after the divorce, since the laws that protect personal rights are not audited as they should be. This situation also puts an importance on the helplines who provide support for FDP women. Moreover, the government should develop stricter regulations to protect refugee women against any type of violent act their ex-spouse might engage in.

Community factors:

Although many institutions and organisations in Turkey carry out studies and activities for FDP, these are not sufficient. For instance, even though many years have passed since the crisis in Syria, the high rate of immigration to the country and the fact that existing refugees establish a new order in the host country instead of returning to their country of origin, cause negative attitudes in the host society. When the economic situation of the country is not stable and the unemployment rate in the country is high, the work carried out for refugees causes the development of hatred towards FDP and the state's immigration policy in the host society, and this results in discrimination. To address these situations, both NGOs and governmental institutions should work on developing new and inclusive ways to improve the social cohesion between the host society and forcibly displaced people. Moreover, media organisations and professionals should be informed and trained to disseminate a more inclusive and peace-making discourse to prevent any polarisation between the host community and forcibly displaced groups.

1.1.2 On meso-level. Interrelationships in the environments in Turkey

Economic factors:

The Turkish government is pushing for potential solutions to cover vulnerable populations, but policy structures and real-life practices do not function in the same way. For instance, when members of VGs do get a chance to be employed, they prefer to be an undocumented worker in the labour force. The reason is that if they are registered workers as part of the system, then they lose their international aid. That is why, while government agencies and related NGOs push for a registered and legal labour force as part of the economic system, VGs themselves do not prefer the official way, so that they can benefit from two ways of gathering economic inputs. Similar to what stated above, policies developed by institutions in relation to daily life practices should be applicable according to real life conditions.

Labour factors:

Unemployment is one of the important problems for Turkey as a country, therefore one of the problems that deeply affects the forcibly displaced groups, considering the high numbers of FDP population in Turkey. In this context, unemployment also causes tension between the host society and the forcibly displaced groups, resulting in an economic vulnerability where refugees are forced to work for low wages. Since most of the female population in the forcibly displaced groups are unemployed, they are generally economically dependent on their spouses, which causes women to be invisible in decision-making processes. Refugees in Turkey are required to obtain a work permit to work in jobs other than seasonal agriculture and animal husbandry. However, considering the refugee population and competitive terms in the work environment, many refugees do not have the chance to work in their professions. Language barriers also play an important role in this issue. In terms of LGBTQI+ community, especially transgender people, are usually forced to earn their living as sex workers. Therefore, they have vulnerabilities in the field of sexual and psychological health. In addition, in very crowded families, especially young boys are forced to work to support the family instead of going to school, which causes an increase in child labour. Since many refugees, including children, work in jobs such as collecting paper and plastic waste, they have to risk their health, especially considering the risks brought by the Covid-19 pandemic.

The vast majority of FDP in Turkey are still in need of humanitarian relief. Although some progress has been made over time, the health-related problems brought along Covid-19, economic problems, and the other possible problems brought along unemployment have produced effects that could weaken the progress that has been made leading to a re-increasing need for humanitarian aid. In addition, during Covid-19 pandemic most of the FDP have lost their jobs and therefore economic difficulties have emerged. Financial difficulties arising due to the lack of a

permanent job has led to an increase in domestic violence. Women employment is almost non-existent, and it has grave negative effects on women's individualisation processes. Due to both economic reasons and the Covid-19 pandemic, women have become more dependent on the family and this situation gives rise to other possible vulnerabilities to emerge in the future. Child labour rates have increased because of economic and educational problems caused by Covid-19.

According to all the factors stated above, policies need to be developed in terms of covering and protecting diverse groups of vulnerable populations. One single approach apparently does not fit for all. Especially, uniquely defined groups within the overall umbrella of vulnerability need to be specifically addressed in policies.

One of the main reasons for this is that the services in the country are currently limited and other economic, social and, in some cases, political problems arise with the increasing immigrant population. Especially with the use of irregular migrants as cheap labour, employment of host country citizens has decreased, and this has created intolerance towards immigrants.

Educational factors:

The fact that some of the refugees are illiterate in their native tongue creates difficulties in learning a new language and makes it difficult to integrate with the host community. For this reason, communication processes with the host society can only be carried out verbally or through interpreters, which brings with it the necessity of continuous language support in daily life practices. It also causes the directive/informative written materials produced to facilitate the process to become dysfunctional. Refugees with higher education levels can both benefit more from the opportunities of the host community and work as intermediaries in communication processes with other refugees.

Considering the conditions brought about by the Covid-19 pandemic, several new vulnerabilities arise in the field of education for refugee children. The poor financial condition of many families and the presence of more than one child, especially in large families, create difficulties for many refugee children who do not have the technological equipment necessary for distance education. According to 2019 data, there are 400.000 school-age refugee children in Turkey who do not attend school. This number alone indicates several vulnerabilities for refugee children both for present and future.

As another vulnerability related to education, unawareness about reproductive health and family planning constitutes a basis that brings along many problems such as difficulties in the education of children, very large families, economic difficulties, and unemployment.

Women are among the HVGs in both the immigrants' home country and Turkey, owing to the patriarchal social structure. Female employment is low, and they also earn less than men. In addition, since they take on the responsibility of housework, their communication with the host society is less, and for this reason, both language learning processes and integration processes with the host society are interrupted. The interruption of the language learning process prevents them from reaching many important rights such as access to education and healthcare services, and access to legal consultancy services. For this reason, the main expectation of immigrants is language education services. This is followed by the right to citizenship, the dissemination of educational services for children, and immigration to European countries.

Education services are also provided for people under international protection. In addition to compulsory education services, refugees and asylum seekers can also participate in free courses provided by the Public Education Centre

of the Ministry of Education. In addition, they can study at universities in Turkey, but they need to pay tuition fees. Due to the civil war in the country, Syrian students are exempt from this tuition. In addition to government agencies, NGOs also provide internationally funded educational services. The vast majority of FDP in Turkey still need humanitarian assistance. Although some progress has been made over time, the impact of Covid-19's health problems, economic difficulties, and other potential problems caused by unemployment may weaken the progress made and generate demand.

Socio-sanitary factors:

Turkey's healthcare and educational system is considered to be strong. People being part of the social security umbrella have access to health care services while people in rural areas need to get these from main cities. The Turkish government is providing universal health care for registered FDP, but these services are not available for those who escape from their country of origin for economic reasons. Apart from this situation, all individuals with asylum seeker and refugee status can benefit from these services. Turkey's General Health Insurance provides access to healthcare services for applicants who are under international protection for at least one year.

According to Özvarış et al. (2020, p. 3) "with 98.8 % of registered refugees residing in urban settings and the vast majority of Covid-19 cases occurring in urban settings, cities play an important role in determining how migrants in Turkey access health services... Major cities such as Istanbul, Ankara, and Izmir are not considered satellite cities and applicants for temporary protection can only reside in these cities temporarily pending their referral to a satellite city. This means they risk losing access to free health services provided in satellite cities (...) when assessing the role of cities during disease outbreak, policies are often implemented at the national or international levels of government, yet it is local public health and political officials who are responsible for outbreak or pandemic management in cities. A lack of governance, poor planning and decentralised health care systems can undermine pandemic responses, often generating confusion, fear, and higher costs" for vulnerable populations.

According to psychological counsellors in Turkish ARU, a vast majority of refugees are unaware of the importance of psychological health, and they did not benefit from these services even before they came to Turkey. Unawareness about psychological health causes the psychological problems caused by the war and migration process to be ignored and new problems to arise. Especially, women and girls who are married at an early age and who are exposed to physical/psychological/sexual abuse and domestic violence are either hesitant to share the problems they experience or not aware of the importance of psychological health and wellbeing, so it becomes difficult to take the necessary precautions in these matters. Although many centres in Turkey provide psychosocial support services for refugees, the number of refugees reaching these centres remains in the minority when compared to the total number of refugees. Refugees who make a living from seasonal agriculture and animal husbandry in rural areas have even less access to these services. The inability to treat psychological problems at this stage creates new risks for them and for their families. Adding the psychological effects of war and forced migration on top of the psychological problems brought on by identity crises, and the fact that the host country also does not have comprehensive laws and practices on LGBTQI+ rights, bring along a new psychological vulnerability especially for transgender individuals who need to earn their living as sex workers. Poverty and unemployment also play a role in the emergence of psychological problems for all groups among FDP.

During the pandemic, the application of HES code (Short for " Hayat Eve Siğar - Life Fits into Home"), which is a code given to every citizen used for sharing people's Covid-19 risk status with institutions, has been made obligatory in public arenas and entrances to government agencies in Turkey. HES code can be obtained with an identity number.

Among the FDP there are those who still do not have an identity number or are in the process to issue identity documents. Since they do not have an identity number yet, they cannot get a HES code without additional support. For this reason, problems arise while entering government agencies. Besides, since there is a language barrier, they have difficulty in communicating with the official authorities regarding this situation.

1.1.3 On macro-level: macro-policies, culture, economic issues, beliefs, etc.

Especially in 2021, with the high depreciation of the Turkish Lira against the Euro and the Dollar, the inflation rate in the country increased, resulting in an increase in the value of goods and services consumed in the country. One of the social groups most affected by this situation is the FDP, as most of them do not have a regular income. In addition, with the increase in the inflation rate, the unemployment rate in the country increased, which again showed a negative effect on the daily life of the FDP and negatively affected the employment of the FDP. With the increase in the unemployment rate, FDP can be forced into unfavourable working conditions by employers. For this reason, cooperation should be made with different organisations, as it happens in the International Labour Organisation (ILO), to protect the work rights and freedoms of the FDP, and it is necessary to make improvements in the existing regulations.

Unfortunately, there is a strong and ongoing polarisation in Turkish society. According to Agirdir (2010, pp. 20-21), Turkish society can be described with the clusters of "moderns", "traditional conservatives", and "religious conservatives". Again, according to Agirdir, "beyond demographic profiling, the profiles of these clusters can be more clearly understood through their view of the developments in current politics. It is expected that the values they have will show their effect while measuring these developments. However, how strict they are in their evaluations and the extent of the difference between their approaches will provide a hint as to the severity of the polarisation." (Agirdir, 2010, p.21). Accordingly, values and identities do matter in the issues that polarise society, which also reflects itself into politics.

FDP who are under international protection in Turkey must register with the Provincial Directorate of Immigration Management in their provinces to benefit from services such as education, social assistance, psychological support, interpreting and access to the labour market.

People who apply for international protection are generally not provided with accommodation. However, it is essential for the applicants to find a house by their own means within the boundaries of the province designated for them and to cover the costs of accommodation themselves. To travel outside of the registered province, it is obligatory to obtain an intercity travel permit from the Provincial Directorate of Migration Management. Regarding the right to work, people with international protection status have it in Turkey, but people with a United Nations (UN) identity do not have the same right.

Although there are laws regarding people with international protection status, there are problems regarding the implementation of these laws. One of the most important reasons for this is that the people under international protection and personnel working in governmental agencies are not informed of the law and its implementation in detail. An immigrant who enters the country for the first time is interviewed, but judicial assistance support is often not provided during this interview. For this reason, immigrants can be deported without learning their legal rights. In addition, the interviews are not recorded, and, for this reason, sufficient evidence cannot be obtained in a possible objection.

The lack of adequate legislation on some specific groups places them in a highly vulnerable position. For instance, there are not enough legal regulations regarding child labour, and this causes the intensive use of child labour. Also, there is no implementation of the domestic law regarding LGBTQI+ community. The absence of any legal rights makes this group invisible in society and makes them highly vulnerable.

Like other citizens living in Turkey, people with temporary protection status can start their own businesses by applying to the relevant institutions and completing the registration process. However, the number of people with Temporary Protection status working in any workplace can be up to ten percent (10%) of the number of Turkish employees. Both the obligation to live in the province appointed by the Provincial Directorate of Migration Management and the employment quota (10%) bring employment problems for people under temporary protection status.

1.2 Issues of diversity

There is no discrimination regarding race in Turkish laws. Anyone with citizenship has access to voting, security, education, etc., and has fundamental rights and freedoms. However, the language of education is Turkish, and individuals from different races and nationalities are educated in Turkish, not in their own language. Gender laws, on the other hand, have been improved over the years. For example, until 2011, according to the Turkish Civil Code, the "head of the house" was considered to be a man, but in 2011, with the shadow reports of many women's rights NGOs, this law was changed to "men and women are equal in marriage". However, although women's rights are protected by laws, these laws remain only as theoretical knowledge and are not applied. Femicide in the country still poses a significant problem. The reason for this is that the patriarchal social structure in the country also shows its effect in the legal system: the number of women working in the legal system is in some ways low and women cannot fully represent themselves. Finally, Turkey withdrew from the Istanbul Convention in 2021, which aims to combat violence against women and domestic violence, so international monitoring of the rights of women and homosexuals in Turkey has become difficult. Also, same-sex marriage is not legal in the country. For this reason, homosexual individuals are denied the right to marry. In addition, although there are no discriminatory laws regarding individuals with different sexual orientations, these individuals are not employed in the society and these individuals are forced into occupations that will harm the individual in every way, such as sex work. There is no expression such as sexual orientation or gender identity in the civil law. This is a sign that LGBTQI+ individuals are recognised at the micro level, but they are ignored at the macro level, and they do not have rights. RTVÚK, the organisation that monitors radio and television broadcasts in Turkey, also fines broadcasts that "normalise" homosexuality and even stops their broadcasting. This is another example of legal discrimination against LGBTQI+ individuals in the country.

Contrary to many injustices and illegalities regarding gender and sexual orientation, Turkish laws do not have any legal discrimination against older people. The Islamic view, which is dominant throughout the country, influences the laws and its implementation, just like the patriarchal view, and for this reason, there are laws that take care of the elderly. Individuals under the age of 18, on the other hand, have all rights under the supervision of their parents. According to Turkish laws, an individual under the age of 18 can be married with the consent of his/her parents. This situation paves the way for child marriages. There is a certain prevalence of child marriage in Turkey, especially in the Eastern and South-eastern Anatolia regions. Moreover, there is an extended expectation that the girl will be held responsible for housework and the boy will be educated and become a professional in the future. Both these situations caused girls to be deprived of upper secondary education, because basic education only covered the first eight years of education. As of 2012, compulsory education has been updated to 12 years, until the end of high school, and this law amendment is aimed to protect the basic education rights of girls. However, the existence of

laws that are not really implemented and the lack of control, which is a common problem at the macro level in Turkey, is also observed here. There are no specific legal exclusions for persons with disabilities. On the contrary, state institutions and organisations have an obligation to employ at least 3% of people with disabilities.

Supervision of the regulations regarding women and LGBTQI+ community: The basis of legal proposals to be made in the context of Turkey should be women and LGBTQI+ individuals, who are the most vulnerable groups in the country. Laws in some ways restrict the rights and freedoms of these individuals and this causes them to experience discrimination in different ways. First of all, although there are some fundamental rights regarding women and LGBTQI+ individuals, these rights are not properly implemented and supervised. For this reason, an international supervisory board should be established for the development of new laws, improvement, and implementation of existing laws. This supervisory board should consist of individuals of different languages, religions, races, genders, nationalities, ages and sexual orientations, and the decisions of this board should be protected by international laws. While carrying out its activities, the supervisory board should cooperate with local NGOs and consider the shadow reports to be prepared by local NGOs.

Employment quota for women and LGBTQI+ community: Another legal proposal to be made is to determine the compulsory employment rate of women and LGBTQI+ individuals in public institutions and organisations. Employment of women and especially LGBTQI+ individuals in public institutions and organisations is very low and they are generally employed in positions such as secretaries. In managerial positions, more male employees are preferred because all duties and responsibilities related to home, family and children are assigned to women. This situation reduces the performance of women in the eyes of employers. Since LGBTQI+ individuals are ignored in the patriarchal structure, they cannot take charge in public institutions and organisations, or they have to hide their identities. Although there is no legal obstacle, they are not employed due to the general prejudice prevailing in the society. With the compulsory employment quota for women and LGBTQI+ individuals, these individuals will not only be able to obtain their economic freedom in a dignified manner, but also will increase their representation in the society. With the increase of their representation, the way to break the prejudice existing in the society will be opened.

Increasing aid for orphans and disabled people: The state and some NGOs carry out aid activities for orphans and disabled people, but these aid activities are not sufficient. The number of aid activities should be increased, enabling more people to reach the service. In addition, appropriations for already existing relief activities need to be increased.

Creating an immigrant policy: All over the world, and especially in Turkey, the number of migrants is increasing every day. All countries could be adversely affected if they made no plans. For this reason, an immigrant policy should be made. A real formula should be created with policies to be done with experts, organisations, institutions such as the EU and the UN, all over the world.

Investment in crisis areas: Businesspeople from Turkey and the world must increase employment in these regions by investing in crisis regions. In this way, both employment in crisis areas will be eliminated and a possible economic crisis in the host country will be prevented. The government should apply tax deductions to employers employing FDP or the state should cover their first three months' salary.

Psycho-social support for staff working with vulnerable groups: Because the stress levels of people working with vulnerable groups are high, these personnel should receive regular rehabilitation treatment. Staff working with vulnerable groups should be supported both economically and psychologically. These personnel will feel better and provide better service with the support of the state. We have depletion levels according to the jobs we work. People

who work with vulnerable groups get tired much faster psychologically. NGOs or organisations like the EU must definitely work on this issue. Rehabilitation of the staff working to deal with migration should be a project.

Local media education: Media is one of the channels where hate speech is used the most. It is very difficult for FDP to be accepted in society. For this reason, there should be some sanctions on their representation in the media. With these sanctions, hatred that may occur in the society can be prevented. Care should be taken in the news language. In interviews, racial and national words should not be included, and especially local media should be educated on this issue.

Increasing health services: The health of FDP indirectly affects the health of the host community. For this reason, reproductive health services, child health services, mental health services, services for the control of infectious diseases and services for the control of chronic diseases should be increased.

Increasing interpreter support: Some of the interviewees also made recommendations for increasing interpreter support in institutions such as courthouses and hospitals. It is a common demand of vulnerable groups. Although security and health services are free, these services cannot be fully used due to language barriers. Individuals are unable to communicate with law enforcement and health personnel due to language barriers, and therefore find it difficult to get support in case of any problem. When faced with such a situation, they have only two options. These include hiring paid translators and getting close support in Turkish. Most of the time, they cannot evaluate this requirement because they do not have sufficient budget for paid translators. Since it is very difficult to find a Turkish-speaking close-up at every need, they usually stay on their own in case of problems. For this reason, they have communication problems. Because of these communication problems, they do not want to apply to the competent authorities in case of a problem, which negatively affects the interaction of immigrants with the local people and their use of right-seeking mechanisms.

1.3 Successful practices

Some of the services provided in Turkey are as follows:

- Turkish and Arabic language education.
- Psycho-social support.
- Sexual and reproductive health education.
- Primary health care.
- Interpreter support.
- Ticket support for transportation.
- Vocational courses.
- Hobby courses.
- Free education services.
- Free healthcare services.
- Cash-Based Interventions.
- Protection Services.
- Shelter.

Most of the interviewees stated that their psycho-social support helped reduce the effects of their trauma. The centre where they registered provides them an environment in which they can socialise. Thus, it provides a social

environment especially for women who cannot go out of their homes and cannot communicate with people other than their family members.

During the FDP interviews which were held in the first year of the project, interviewees state that they want the number of centres where they receive language, health, interpreters, and vocational course services to increase. They also expressed the need to increase the number of interpreters in health units. Some of the interviewees expressed their problems finding a house in Turkey. They stated that they need a person / institution to mediate in the process of finding a home. They expressed their demands to improve and increase employment opportunities for refugees.

In general terms, they are quite satisfied with the services (e.g., language, vocational training, and hobby courses) in women's health and counselling centres for refugees. With the training and activities in these centres, they can meet and socialise with the local people. In addition, they receive psycho-social support in the centres for the treatment of bad experiences in their own country and during their travels. Thanks to psycho-social support, the processes of adaptation to the new country and the processes of socialisation with the local people are accelerated by feeling better. The language barrier, which is the biggest problem, disappears with the language training provided. Thus, they can communicate with the local people. A significant example needs to be shared from the city of Izmir. Izmir City Council established "Refugee Women Council" as behalf of the city Council to understand, analyse and provide solutions for refugee women-vulnerable groups that are defined by the groups themselves.

In the following, some of the main good practices stated by the stakeholders and ARU members are also listed:

- There are associations they have established themselves: With this association, they can socialise and thus support each other economically and psychologically and help each other in daily life. They become aware of the state and other NGO-supported centres through these associations and have increased access to assistance.
- Children can access educational services for free: One of the most positive practices is that children can access educational services for free. Children represent the future of a country. Integration into the host country is much easier for children. Thus, they will have a more harmonious life with the host country in the future.
- State supported and NGO supported centres: Dealing with government forces displaced people in Turkey and supported NGOs have also assisted other institutions. Many guidance teachers work in these institutions. With these guidance services, FDP adapt to the host country more easily. By finding the opportunity to learn the city they live in, they both can handle their own business and get the opportunity to socialise with the host community. The EU also provides financial support to such institutions. There are women's health and counselling centres for forced displaced people. This is also very important because one of the main problems with forced displaced people is reproductive health. Through these centres, they can learn about reproductive health and access sexual health treatments.
- Refugee Rights Commission: The Bar Association has a Refugee Rights Commission. There is a commission and a group of lawyers to deal with the refugees' cases. They can get support from this commission in case of any problem. There are also various units in universities. Many NGOs also work for FDP.
- Educational brochures and booklets: Republic of Turkey, Amnesty International, the UN and many other organisations forcibly press educational brochures and booklets about the people who were displaced and

distribute them. These brochures and booklets are printed in Turkish and Arabic and aim to raise awareness of both the forced displaced people and the host community.

- **Free health services:** With the free health services, both the health of the FDP and the health of the host community are improved. This prevents the propagation of some diseases that may occur in unsanitary conditions.

1.4 Summary

Considering the previous points as the primary sources of vulnerability in Turkey on each socio-ecological level, the most relevant and important policy recommendations are listed below.

Micro Level: Poverty, patriarchy, illiteracy or low education level, language barrier, gender identity, sex, nationality, unemployment, war trauma, being exposed to various forms of violence/abuse are among the micro-level issues that determine Turkey's vulnerability context.

Meso Level: Strong legal measures on various forms of activism, cultural values and identities, socio-economic conditions which differs based on the regions in Turkey, time-limited health services, paid university education, paid language education in institutions that can issue language proficiency certificates, are among the meso-level issues that determine Turkey's vulnerability context.

Macro Level: Excessive number of FDP residing in Turkey, a lack of governance, poor planning and decentralised health care systems that can undermine pandemic responses, lack of accommodation support, judicial support for FDP during the interviews with Provincial Directorate of Migration Management, the lack of adequate legislation and/or flaws in the implementation of the law concerning specific groups such as minors, women and LGBTQI+ community and the employment quota are among the macro-level issues that determine Turkey's vulnerability context.

According to the levels defined above:

- While developing policies related to the vulnerable groups, it is necessary to be aware that in a country like Turkey with a high amount of vulnerable group populations, the "one size fits all approach" to cover vulnerable groups may not function in various contexts. According to this, policies for general and broad coverage need to be developed, while "narrow-casting" approaches on behalf of policies need to be developed to address the needs of vulnerable groups.
- While policies are being developed, they must be applicable to real life practices. While vulnerable groups (refugees) do prefer and/or benefit from having international protection, they also try to be part of the labour force in the host country. Accordingly, the laws and policies developed in the country in some ways should not create a kind of conflict of interest from the perspective of vulnerable groups.
- Policies need to be developed with NGOs and vulnerable groups. Vulnerable groups indicate that policy making should not be like "talking about us", "talking for us", but rather it must be "talking with us". Then, they state that they see themselves in the meaning of policies as they are part of policy making.

2 Policy brief summarising the main results and findings of the project for stakeholders from CESIE (Italy)

2.1 Vulnerability

2.1.1 On micro-level. Considerations about personal conditions and features

Individual factors:

Access to specialised medical care may pose a challenge for populations affected by the trauma of displacement. At community level, migrants' difficulties in accessing public health services have been identified as due to bureaucratic, cultural and information barriers. This translates in a greater use of emergency hospital services among migrants compared with the Italian population. This health care utilisation profile, on an emergency basis, is a source of concern as it suggests that migrants might not access prevention and promotion services and lack continuity of care. This explains the growing number of emergency admittances and hospitalisations for acute psychiatric disorders among migrants.

Briefly, in terms of social and health services, there is still a lack of planning, tools and working practices that are important to be adapted to individuals coming from very different socio-geographical areas - as culture and gender-oriented approaches allow to overcome prejudices about pathologies, including mental disorders, ensuring a system of reception and care services which considered gender issues. There is a risk that current interventions, whether in formal or non-formal education settings, rely too heavily on foreign cultural norms that do not translate well unless adapted to local contexts and perceptions of mental health and well-being needs. In particular, gynaecological and specialist examinations (PAP tests, ultrasounds, etc.) should be carried out exclusively by professional female staff.

Outpatient services should have no waiting lists. Facilitated routes for persons in a particularly vulnerable condition are in place through structured collaborations with other public and private health services.

Intra-family factors:

As stated by inclusion actors and professionals working in Palermo, particularly with HV FDP women in urban contexts "(...) with Covid-19 home lockdown restrictions, there have been explosive intra-familiar situations resulting in severe family violence. However, it is not only about physical but also the "invisible" violence of total subordination of one family member to another (husband / wife, parent / child). There has been a general increase in the phenomena of emotional unease among foreign families, particularly challenging situations for women who hardly rely on the health-social support system of the public service for fear of social services removing their children from home; they do not want to expose themselves too much as often they are irregularly staying in the country. This also leads to reluctance in visiting doctors in general and many FDP women are still unaware that they are entitled access to paediatrician for their children, by law"¹.

In this view, there is a need to update existing protocols to ensure the right of information particularly for HV FDP women, and women with children should be ensured as stipulated by law, receiving information about their rights,

¹ Information provided by ANTHROPOLOGY AND GEOCLINICAL PSYCHOLOGY centre, Palermo. The Centre provides consultancy in the field of Ethno psychology, both for the treatment of patients and for carrying out advocacy actions; specialised in clinical supervision in reception centres for unaccompanied minors, refugees and asylum seekers.

including that of being able to apply for international protection, in a form and language they can effectively understand.

Community factors:

Participation at the local level is often the first type of participation for newly-arrived migrants in the receiving society, and the platform upon which the first steps towards integration occur. This is also an important platform for developing a feeling of inclusion in the receiving society among migrants. Civil participation promotes real-life face-to-face interaction among individuals and between individuals and the community. There is a growing presence of marginalised FDP and asylum seekers hosted by the disorganised and sometimes corrupted Italian reception system. This is problematic for various reasons. On the one hand, this very visible migrant population encourages the Italian population to lump old and new migrants together into a single stigmatised population. On the other, the migrant population itself is driven to buy into a discourse distinguishing between “integrated” migrants (“us”) and newcomers (“them”). With all the funds and the political and media attention (negatively) given to the latter, the former – those once hailed as the “agents of development” – feel now unfairly scapegoated by Italian public opinion. Therefore, it is paramount to protect solidarity among Forcibly Displaced individuals and communities.

2.1.2 On meso-level. Interrelationships in the environments in Italy

Economic factors:

In 2021, migrants in irregular situation² or so called "temporarily present foreigners" (people without a work permit or residency papers and unaccompanied minors) are more than 25,000 throughout Sicily (560,000 at national level) but for the national and regional government they are invisible. Excluded from any form of protection and prevention, because without a residence permit, without tax code, residence, or fixed abode. They often live in the suburbs of Italian cities but are cut off from the anti-covid vaccination.

In practice, the measure responded to a strategic economic interest in ensuring that essential sectors had enough workers rather than focusing on a rights-based approach. Overall, 220,000 people applied under the program, just under a third of the estimated 690,000 undocumented migrants in Italy.

In this view of the above, the 2020 REGULARISATION program appears even more paradoxical for a measure aiming to address irregular work as the conditions required to apply for the six months residence permit to look for jobs significantly limit its scope, leaving out numerous migrants in conditions of irregularity and precariousness, including many of those affected by the so-called ‘Salvini Decrees’. Moreover, by requiring people to prove, through appropriate official documents, that they have worked in one of eligible sectors, the provision excludes all migrants who have worked in undeclared conditions in these sectors. Therefore, Labour Policies should be duly assessed in terms of constitutional legitimacy to avoid differentiating the access to welfare provisions on grounds of nationality or type of residence permit (namely the EU long-term residence permit) as it indirectly discriminates FDP and third-country citizens on grounds of nationality, but possibly also of other vulnerability factors, such as disability or age.

Housing factors:

² Over the past two years, Italy has rejected record numbers of asylum claims, including due to the abolition of the humanitarian leave to remain in 2018. Between January 2019 and mid-May 2020, more than 91,000 asylum claims were rejected; the overall rejection rate at first instance was 80 percent. <https://reliefweb.int/report/italy/italy-flawed-migrant-regularization-program>

By analysing further FDP communities in Italy and turning focus to peripheral and rural areas, a Multidimensional Vulnerability Assessment Model has mapped at national level informal settlements inhabited mainly by refugees who have never entered the institutional reception system or have left it before their social inclusion process was completed. In this specific peripheral and rural context areas vulnerabilities are inverted. Men are more vulnerable on most Vulnerability Dimensions, except employment (Busetta et al. 2016).

1. Shelter: living in a settlement with no accommodation in buildings for all residents.
2. Objective health: having had a health problem not met by a formal medical assistance.
3. Subjective health: bad or very bad self-reported general health.
4. Family support: not having any non-dependent family member living in Italy.
5. Legal status: having no current legal right to reside in Italy.
6. Literacy: no formal education and no ability to read or write.
7. Employment: not in employment in Italy.

Young males are even more vulnerable to direct experiences of unpaid or forced work and of being held against their will. Differences by age are not pronounced, but younger people have worse living conditions; while older people are less likely to have a legal status. Male refugees and asylum seekers who have been in Italy for longer are less vulnerable, but the opposite is true for females. Duration of residence is also an important predictor of vulnerability, but only for men. Therefore, in informal settlements FDP are significantly more vulnerable if: Male, young, single, recently arrived, living in smaller settlements. As vulnerabilities express in different contexts, the concept of vulnerability should be reassessed and a new individual assessment model and tools for Italy should be designed and implemented.

Labour factors:

The 'Regularisation Program' for migrants in irregular situation was adopted in May 2020 to "guarantee adequate protection of individual and collective health" and "facilitate the emergence of irregular employment relationships" – to bring informal and undocumented work out of the shadows. Concern about inadequate, unsanitary housing and obstacles to health care amid the public health emergency caused by Covid-19 was one of the arguments in favour of the regularisation program. By law, undocumented migrants in Italy can obtain a temporary health card that entitles them to care analogous to that available to other residents with legal permits and citizens. Nevertheless, Italian organisations providing services to migrants have documented logistical and bureaucratic obstacles people face in obtaining the temporary health card and finding healthcare services, including lack of information, inability to register due to the lack of a formal address, linguistic barriers, and mistrust in public authorities.

Educational factors:

As highlighted by the Council Resolution on a strategic framework for European cooperation in education and training towards the European Education Area and beyond (2021-2030) 2021/C 66/01³, by ensuring quality and inclusive education and training for all, Member States can further reduce social, economic, and cultural inequalities.

³ Council Resolution on a strategic framework for European cooperation in education and training towards the European Education Area and beyond (2021-2030) <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/media/48584/st06289-re01-en21.pdf>

However, across Europe, learners from disadvantaged backgrounds, including from rural and remote areas, are overrepresented among underachievers and the Covid-19 pandemic has highlighted even more starkly the importance of equity and inclusion in education and training. It is of utmost importance to guarantee the same opportunity for all asylum seekers. Today uneven reception standards throughout the country and a fragmented asylum system generate strong inequalities in the treatment of and possibilities for asylum seekers of different profiles, concerning race, gender, sexual orientation, age, disabilities. In this view, Adult Education plays a vital role in the current migration and refugee situation in Europe. What is missing from the debate is a focus on public policies (including education) to maximise the benefits of migration, to support people to integrate into society and to tackle the local pressures on services and infrastructure.

The Covid-19 crisis demonstrated that education and training systems must be sufficiently flexible and resistant to interruptions in their regular cycles and proved that EU countries have the capacity to find solutions to continue the delivery of teaching and learning processes in different ways and contexts, and to ensure that all learners, irrespective of their socioeconomic background or learning needs, continue to learn. The same applies for the framework of European cooperation, which should remain flexible enough to respond to both current and future challenges, including in the context of the European Education Area⁴.

Socio-sanitary factors:

In Italy there is no distinction between asylum seekers benefitting from material reception conditions and those who are out of the reception system since all asylum seekers benefit from the National Health System.

The right to medical assistance should not expire in the process of the renewal of the permit of stay, however in practice, asylum seekers with an expired permit of stay have no guarantee of access to non-urgent sanitary treatments for a significant length of time due to the bureaucratic delays in the renewal procedure.

This also means that where asylum seekers do not have a domicile to renew their permit of stay, for example because their accommodation right has been revoked, they cannot renew the health card. Medical assistance is extended to each regularly resident family member under the applicant's care in Italy and is recognised for new-born babies of parents registered with the National Health System.

Still nowadays one of the most relevant obstacles to access health services is the language barrier; it ultimately impacts negatively on health-care access (not addressing general doctors; going to hospital only in case of threatening conditions); the use of emergency services remains the most common practice among migrant/minority populations in Italy.

2.1.3 On macro-level: macro-policies, culture, economic issues, believes, etc.

Laws, decrees, and multitude of amendments related to emigration and immigration have been shaping Italy's inclusion policies and practices, creating administrative and legal indeterminacy. This complex framework, including legislative novelties and their interpretations is not favourable for acquiring an accurate knowledge on the phenomenon. Actually, it creates series of obstacles that hinder the effective and good outcome of projects.

⁴ Council Resolution on a strategic framework for European cooperation in education and training towards the European Education Area and beyond (2021-2030) <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/media/48584/st06289-re01-en21.pdf>

Passive labour policies and welfare interventions towards migrants are useless if these simply mitigate the need without aiming at full individual autonomy. Instead, there lies a risk of having the opposite effect since the capacity of people who are constantly supported might decay and fail to be empowered. Social policies that provide goods and services are therefore desirable if they expect a commitment on behalf of beneficiaries who should also participate in the planning (models of self-construction or self-recovery). In this way costs are reduced, the number of potential beneficiaries increases, and they do not feel humiliated or forced to participate passively in a process of cultural assimilation.

2.2 Issues of diversity

No systematic evaluation of integration policies of FDP is carried out in Italy, except for the interventions funded through the EU's Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund (AMIF).

Therefore, in general terms, issues of diversity (race, gender, sexual identity and orientation, age, disabilities) need to be embedded into a structured benchmarking model as this helps to target, implement, and assess the effect of policies and practices and to ensure the level of impact of FDPs' inclusion processes. Actors need specific criteria and indicators to work with, in order to come up with a planned-for output and outcome. It allows actors to learn what works and what does not, as well as what needs to be improved or changed. Evidence of the work carried out can be used to help improve the overall performance and to maximise the efforts to guarantee the fulfilment of the fundamental rights of the most vulnerable migrants. The periodic monitoring of progress towards the set objectives through systematic collection and analysis of internationally comparable data provides an essential contribution towards evidence-informed policy making.

In many institutions there are no criteria as to the quality of the partners, the practices, and their sustainability. Assessment is most often regarded as number crushing that might satisfy the statisticians, but often it does not reveal anything about the inherent and planned-for quality of clearly defined and sustainable targets.

Inclusion strategies and practices should be benchmarked at macro-level (policy-makers and public authorities that plan and finance inclusion strategies) and at meso-micro level (beneficiaries, actors and Institutions that implement and report about inclusion practices) being a valuable opportunity to share knowledge and experience, identify gaps in current practices and hence opportunities for improvement, highlight new approaches and-or systems as well as ideas and bring a critical external focus to any review process.

Social and health services:

In terms of social and health services, there is still a lack of planning, tools and working practices adapted to individuals coming from very different areas and cultures. This is most evident in the Sicilian context.

The request for psychological and psychiatric counselling, despite the emergence of a need, is not easy either because of the inaccessibility of the services and the difficulty in acknowledging the demand, or because sometimes the services are unable to offer a competent answer given the complexity of a transcultural intervention. To offer an adequate service, it seems fundamental to combine human resources and skills. There is a strong discomfort among social and health professionals working with FDP in the face of disappointing results in the care of users from other cultural universes. In the health field, policy guidelines should deal with the inadequacy of theories unable to understand disorders and behaviours not provided for in the classic manuals. In these cases, it is necessary to count on the work of multidisciplinary teams and local health services who should cooperate with all the subjects who

come into contact with beneficiaries of international protection or asylum seekers – reception centre operators, educators, lawyers.

Sexual orientation and gender identity:

In Italy, as in many European countries, no statistical data are collected on requests for international protection based on persecutions due to sexual orientation or gender identity (so-called SOGI). Therefore, it is not possible to know how many people apply for asylum under Article 1A (2) of the 1951 Convention relating to the Status of Refugees and / or its 1967 Protocol. In Italy there are still no structures dedicated exclusively to welcoming LGBTQI+ refugees and migrants, even though the sexual orientation or gender identity is considered relevant in the asylum context. Sexual orientation or gender identity is generally established through an evaluation of the declaration of the asylum seeker and of supporting evidence (if available). Court decisions have been reported that considered credible the sexual orientation based on the declaration of the claimant, without any other evidence.

The procedure for obtaining refugee status for issues related to sexual orientation is particularly complex, as the investigation can rarely be based on documentary and irrefutable evidence. In fact, as stated in the same UNHCR guidelines "The assessment of the applicant's LGBTI identity is essentially a question of credibility" (UNHCR, 2012). Often these people are not informed about their rights and about the possibility of applying for protection as a refugee according to Article 8 of Legislative Decree 251/2007 which offers protection to a "particular social group".

Italy has adopted the good practice according to which the existence of laws condemning homosexuality, in the country of origin, is in itself considered persecutory. Nevertheless, a big obstacle is given by the fact that LGBTQI+ identities are concepts born and formalised in our Western culture and which are also subject to substantial changes within our culture and over time. For this reason, in some cases the linguistic categories that asylum seekers can use to indicate both practices and identities are lacking (even practices and identities are concepts deriving from Western thought). Another underestimated problem is homophobia that the asylum seeker finds in the community of his country of origin, generally the first people he/she comes into contact with when he/she arrives in a foreign country. These interventions (individual interviews to investigate personal circumstances, the need to verify the age declared upon arrival, the referral of vulnerable cases, etc.) should therefore be carried out by third parties, such as specialised staff of the managing body in partnership with any specialised agencies/organisations that may be working in the centres.

2.3 Successful practices

In 2017, the Italian government adopted the National Integration Plan for Persons Entitled to International Protection, as foreseen by decree 18/2014, which transposed the EU's recast Qualification Directive (Directive 2011/95/EU). The plan, to be funded by EU and national financial resources, set out priorities for 2017-2018, including inter-religious and intercultural dialogue, language training, access to education, labour inclusion and vocational training. The main actors responsible for implementing the foreseen measures are local authorities and local public services, with the support of civil society organisations. However, in the end of 2019, the implementation of the plan was limited to pilot actions carried out in three regions, Piedmont, Emilia Romagna, and Calabria, with the collaboration of the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR) which co-drafted the plan.

It is considered extremely important to adopt a second National Plan for Integration, which would be more effective if it is placed within the framework of a wider a broader effort of national re-programming of entry and integration policies aimed at all citizens (as provided for by the T. U, Immigration, Legislative Decree 286/98, art. 3 paragraph 1).

In this regard, to the first Plan of 2017 identified two priority axes (interreligious dialogue and language) which must be updated with priority axes regarding issues of work, health, housing and correct information on the rights and duties of persons enjoying protection.

Recommendations:

- The new National Plan for Integration should consider the current social framework and ensure multiannual planning, with the possibility of periodic reviews.
- Public governance at regional level should be promoted to guarantee uniformity of interventions throughout the country.
- Recognise a system based on widespread and shared responsibility. One cannot disregard collaboration with local authorities or associations of municipalities, with the third sector and the world of voluntary sector, trade associations, companies, schools, etc.
- Encourage the creation of heterogeneous territorial networks through a system of rewards.
- Rewarding the provision of integrated services among the non-profit sector, associations, and public bodies.
- Promote open data - open information platforms with the number of accommodations and the number of reception structures present on the territory, including at municipal level, the number of applicants and the number of applicants and holders, the number of available accommodations, the names of managers and the services offered by the different structures.

Also, a skills recognition system is needed for to assess competences gained outside formal curricula that could finally allow beneficiaries to be involved and selected also on the basis of the experience acquired. A good practice mentioned by different Italian Regions⁵ is the European Qualifications Passport for Refugees (EQPR), a special international tool developed to assess refugee's qualifications for which there is insufficient or missing documentation that should be mainstreamed at national level too.

The European Qualifications Passport for Refugees is a standardised document issued in a project carried out by the Council of Europe and partners. The European Qualifications Passport for Refugees consists of two parts – the assessment part and the explanatory part. The assessment part of the European Qualifications Passport contains information on the highest qualification(s) achieved, academic discipline, other relevant qualifications, as well as relevant job experience and language proficiency (in cases where it is possible to substantiate it). The explanatory part contains information about the status of the document and a short description of the Project.

Although this document does not constitute a formal recognition act, it summarises and presents available information on the applicant's educational level, work experience and language proficiency. The evaluation methodology is a combination of an assessment of available documentation and the use of a structured interview. Thus, the document provides credible information that can be relevant in connection with applications for employment, internships, qualification courses and admission to studies.

Recommendations:

⁵ Conference of the regions and autonomous provinces "Position on the update of the National Integration National Integration Plan for holders of International Protection", 23/04/2020 [20/64/CR10/C15]
<http://www.regioni.it/download/conferenze/610772/>

- Further develop a methodology which would be acceptable to universities and employers.
- Spread the word about the EQPR among refugees, creating trust in the process.
- On-line interviews – establish a model to ensure that they are as credible as a face-to-face interview.
- Make the EQPR accepted in more countries.

2.4 Summary

Overcome persisting downward labour inclusion and segregation in the low-wage, unprotected sectors of the labour market. The great majority of FDP are still confined to low-wage and menial occupations. The Italian model of downward labour inclusion has hampered, or at least limited, migrants' access to better paid, more protected, and more qualified jobs (e.g., managers, department head, white-collar jobs, technicians, and professionals). In addition, migrant entrepreneurs often have no other option than to enter into poor niche or already saturated economic sectors – placing their business activities into a position of weakness and dependency. While there are of course successful exceptions to this rule, immigrant independent workers, as well as employee, generally face several visible and invisible barriers in their path of social and economic affirmation.

Eradicate barriers to education and specialised training. FDP face a series of structural barriers and problems in accessing the educational and academic system. Recognition of diplomas, certifications and skills gained abroad remains complicated. Schools, teachers, and the educational system are not well equipped to manage multi-ethnic classrooms and pupils, and they struggle to deal with issues linked to multiculturalism. Foreigners have very few opportunities when it comes to accessing high skill qualifications, specialised training courses or grants. Therefore, an effective and efficient investment in education and training is a prerequisite for enhancing quality and inclusiveness of the education and training systems and improving the education outcomes, as well as for driving sustainable growth, improving wellbeing, and building a more inclusive society.

Promote democratic access to political and citizenship rights. FDP and third country nationals in general still have very limited access to political and citizenship rights. The right to vote at national level is granted only to Italian citizens, and only citizens of EU member states are entitled to vote in local elections. The extremely limited political participation of migrants impacts priorities in national politics. Political parties and politicians have no interest in gaining the support of a population that has no voting powers, and rather prefer to give in to public fears and to the social unease of the Italian lower classes. The current Citizenship law, last amended in 1992, incorporates a conception of nationality based on a “right of blood” or parentage, and therefore strongly penalises foreign residents as well as persons born in the country from third-country nationals.

Boost on FDP's political representation and upward social mobility. FDP communities still lack influential leadership, while organisations representing diaspora and migrants are still not fully integrated in the Italian political landscape. FDP and people of foreign background are still excluded from the political and economic establishment. They are denied access to powerful, influential, visible, and prestigious positions. Until now, there have been only a handful of journalists, TV hosts, commentators, experts, intellectuals, scientists, writers and artists, administrators, and politicians with a foreign background.

Fight xenophobic and nationalist discourse targeting migrants. Discriminatory actions barring migrants from social services and provisions are now institutionally legitimised, while Italy's international protection commitments – as shown by the ongoing conflict with international NGOs over search and rescue operations in the Mediterranean – are routinely challenged and questioned. It is not by chance that hate speech and racist acts and behaviours towards immigrants have since multiplied, and now fill the pages of newspapers almost daily (Lunaria, 2019).

3 Policy brief summarising the main results and findings of the project for stakeholders from Complutense University of Madrid (Spain)

3.1 Vulnerability

3.1.1 On micro-level. Considerations about personal conditions and features

Individual factors:

FDP with mental health problems derived from the violence they have suffered in transit do not receive adequate care, on many occasions, due to the lack of knowledge they have about their rights in health centres. The same happens with people with disabilities: until their refugee status is recognised, they do not receive full attention. During the asylum application process, the specific needs of the most vulnerable groups regarding mental health care and situations of disability should be considered.

Intrafamily factors:

Some organisations have detected that many couples do not divorce because of the economic cost that it entails. This is true even for some women who experience gender-based violence, especially those who come from more patriarchal cultures. When these problems are detected, there should be action protocols that accompany women and guarantee them protection throughout the process, until they can be autonomous. The current aid is partial and due to the scarcity of resources, it is very rarely possible to carry out an adequate follow-up. On the other hand, asylum seekers should be better informed about the consequences of seeking asylum in the first EU country they arrive in. Many of them unknown these consequences, so they sign a paper that they do not understand and consequently, the members of the same family cannot regroup until years later. The greatest psychological impact of these situations occurs in minors.

Community factors:

The roots that the most vulnerable groups may have in destination countries should be considered before granting them the final destination. Depending on the specific characteristics of a vulnerable group, the final destination in which that group has more opportunities and support networks for its social inclusion should also be considered. It should be a priority final destinations for women with children. In the case of emergency evacuations, in conflicts such as Afghanistan, the departure of women and women with children should have been prioritised, knowing that they would suffer the greatest reprisals. However, there has been a gender bias and the institutions have mostly evacuated men and their families. Existing gender biases in emergency evacuations should be reviewed.

3.1.2 On meso-level. Interrelationships in the environments in Spain

Economic factors:

The participating entities consider that the time and resources allocated to the inclusion of VGs among the FDP are not sufficient. When the assistance ends, there are many who have not yet been able to be economically autonomous. To improve this situation, it would be necessary to implement more help with the language and improve the offer of free courses to be able to work. On the other hand, FDP are unaware of their own rights and possible help. Given this lack of information, many people are left out of the asylum application system. Full information should be offered to asylum seekers about the aid and subsidies to which they are eligible. In addition, it would be necessary to improve the labour insertion of FDP. Due to different reasons, such as scarce resources or

even occupational stereotypes, the training and previous experience of each person are not considered. This causes they are driven to professional activities such as cleaning and caring for the elderly are assigned, which are very precarious professional activities that are stereotypically associated with women and migrants.

Housing factors:

FDP experience serious problems of access to housing, since even with guarantees they do not want to rent to them. Landlords are unaware of the "Red Card"⁶ and prefer not to rent to FDP. Some people ask Spanish friends to sign the contract, sublet or rent a single room. To improve the great difficulty in finding housing for FDP, public information campaigns should be carried out on what the "Red Card" and the Foreign Resident Identification Number are, as well as reserving public housing from the Administration.

Labour factors:

Jobs should not be incompatible with social aid and subsidies until the former do not provide sufficient remuneration and are full-time. Asylum seekers do not accept jobs so as not to lose those subsidies, or they work "under the table". In this way, they cannot justify their working life or apply for their residence permit because of social roots, and if the processes are delayed or if the asylum is denied, these people suddenly find themselves in an irregular situation. Then they must ask for other help and they may not be able to ask for it on time, so they are left out of the system, and they can only receive help from Samur Social. Once people depend on Samur Social, their diversity is not considered. They are left with nothing, even at risk of being deported. Neighbourhood associations are well organised and sometimes they are the ones who support and feed these people. It is important to generate processes that give rise to the creation of networks, encourage belonging and set up support groups for vulnerable people among FDP. For example, facilitating the work of neighbourhood associations that assist VGs.

The authorisation to be able to work should be accelerated, so they can get out of that vulnerability. There is a lack of knowledge among employers regarding the possibility of hiring FDP and, when in doubt, they prefer to hire other people. Due to the labour situation in Spain, which is also unfavourable for Spanish nationals, many employers take advantage of the need by increasing their precariousness and working "under the table". There is a great lack of knowledge of the "Red Card" and the renewal processes. It is necessary to work on employability and facilitate hiring FDP. It would be necessary to carry out information campaigns between companies and workers about the situation of the FDP and involve the trade unions. Especially in the case of small and medium businesses, which are the most numerous in Spain. Positive discrimination actions could be applied, such as reserving a quota to hire, as happens with people with disabilities.

Educational factors:

Educational centres tend to lack transitional classrooms, so students do not adapt and often repeat a year. During compulsory studies, some aid is implemented, but not later. The system does not guarantee access to university education. They need support, since they cannot spend 4 years studying if their survival is not guaranteed. For this reason, a curricular adaptation is necessary at university, which does not yet exist, so that the VGs among FDP could have better access and success at university. In addition, the processes of homologation of academic degrees are long and expensive. Validation of studies should be facilitated to ensure a better social inclusion. For instance,

⁶ Official identification document for asylum seekers in Spain.

guaranteeing advice for the homologation of academic titles and that these processes are free and shorter in the case of VGs.

Socio-sanitary factors:

In Spain, social care policies are designed for people who already have access to social health systems, but there is more vulnerability for people who are in the process (asylum seekers) and NGOs must collaborate in their care. On the other hand, the same attention and inclusion policies are not carried out throughout the Spanish territory, it depends on each region within the country. An example of this is the access to the health system. At the state level, in Spain, it is necessary to equate social care policies since there is inequality in the social care and inclusion of FDP depending on the specific region. Socio-health care has worsened since the pandemic also for Spanish nationals, but even more in the case of FDP. The procedures of the FDP take longer than those of any citizen, as this is the case of the access to specialist doctors, medical prescriptions, or changes of health centres. Without the support of specialised entities and organisations, it would be impossible to access free and universal healthcare in Spain for VGs among FDP. In addition, the cross-cultural approach in mental health is lacking. There are cases in which health professionals are not identifying situations of high vulnerability due to the lack of mediators, for instance in situations of trafficking and gender violence (if you go to the doctor with the abuser, etc.). In health centres, sometimes they do not know what the “Red Card” is, and they issue invoices because they confuse them with tourists. There are complicated administrative processes: different documents, procedures... Free and universal healthcare should be guaranteed by the Administrations, including the cross-cultural approach, without VGs having the need to resort to NGOs or to other types of organisations. Information campaigns should be carried out in health centres so that administrative staff are aware of the “Red Card” and refugees do not have problems with health care.

It is also necessary to improve training because international protection applicants did not reach municipal services.

3.1.3 On macro-level: macro-policies, culture, economic issues, believes, etc.

Due to the conflict in Ukraine and the humanitarian crisis caused by it, the European Union has decided to streamline the asylum application processes for Ukrainian citizens. This shows that it is possible to change the regulations if there is the will to do so. Speeding up the asylum application procedures for Ukrainian citizens without increasing resources will imply that the Spanish asylum system will become even more overloaded. If more resources are not allocated, the slowdown in the migratory processes of the rest of the nationalities will give rise to many people suddenly finding themselves in an irregular situation, increasing their vulnerability.

The pandemic has had very negative consequences on the social care and inclusion of FDP in Spain. Before, the policies for refugees were better, but since the 2008 crisis they have taken steps back in areas such as labour or economics. With the geopolitical conflicts and the social crisis, the different cases make the refugees even more vulnerable. Some FDP have even been left homeless or forced to engage in sex work. They must ask for social services again when they thought it was not going to be necessary. To alleviate these effects, the Minimum Vital Income was applied in Spain, but its application was very complicated for people who do not speak the language or lack the necessary skills for these procedures. In addition, not enough human resources were allocated for its processing. Many administrative procedures are being carried out online, but this is not adapted to the most vulnerable groups, who tend to suffer from a greater digital divide.

Racism:

There are cases of racism in public administration. In addition, asylum seekers mistrust institutions and they fear being reported for an irregular status if they go to the doctor. These bad practices in public administration due to racism should be penalised. Reporting channels should be facilitated, as FDP fear further reprisals if they report these situations. Spanish legislation already considers inspections to identify abusive practices against VGs, but they are not put into practice. More inspections are needed (control mechanisms and monitoring of public employees), as well as channels allowing anonymous reporting, especially in the case of public administration, but also in the private and labour spheres. An example of this would be that diversity was part of the subjects for the public examinations. Regarding VGs, there have been communication campaigns promoted by Vox, a far-right party, that, spreading false information about these groups, and tried, for instance, to criminalise unaccompanied minors. This type of speech should be condemned, it could even be classified as a hate crime.

3.2 *Issues of diversity*

All issues of diversity (such as race, gender, sexual orientation, age, disabilities, etc.), along with the support network, influence the social care and inclusion of FDP, since people who lack a true support network are more vulnerable. These issues must be considered since each person has different needs. However, they are currently not considered. Especially in the case of gender identity, trans and/or racialised people, since they are intersections that also affect refugees. Trans people sometimes suffer discrimination even from their own associations, especially if they are racialised women. There is a belief that poverty and exclusion haunt a person for life if they are vulnerable. Budgets need to be increased so that social care can be tailored to the profile of asylum seekers and their specific needs. When defining the different vulnerable groups that apply for international protection, an intersectional approach should be adopted due to the forms of oppression suffered, including the gender perspective.

Mental health and disability are identified with vulnerable groups and their vital times are not parallel to legal times. Therefore, to these issues of diversity it would be necessary to add people who have suffered severe trauma; since there are no specific programs for them and they will have greater difficulties. These people lack more time during the processes, so they are left out of the system in the same period as other people who do not have these added difficulties. It is necessary to adapt the times of the social care and inclusion processes of VGs to their greater needs. Even so, in general terms, the social care and inclusion phases of all FDP groups must be better adjusted so that their inclusion and adaptation is effective, providing more resources to the refugees before the last phase.

The profiles of the group in their country of origin are not sufficiently considered to be adapted to their new life in the destination country. Particularity is not sought, but a global and egalitarian response. The system in Spain is saturated by geopolitical crises, also internal, and that is why refugees are welcomed in cities or territories where their adaptation and inclusion is worse.

Regarding attention to diversity, almost all the recommendations are non-binding, especially in the private sphere. It is part of the voluntary nature of each company without any obligation. An alliance among the Third Sector and other areas would be necessary to manage diversity.

Childhood is a vulnerable group. The figures of suddenly finding themselves in an irregular situation are much higher in minors, both accompanied and unaccompanied. There are also situations in which asylum applications are resolved differently for members of the same family, for example, asylum is granted to children but not to parents. It would be necessary to take these data into account and to guarantee more child protection in practice.

Although there are mental health care services within the reception system, their access must be guaranteed and the transcultural approach applied, especially in the case of VGs among the FDP. As well as guaranteeing translation and interpretation systems, since sometimes they do not exist, or they are unsuitable. This cross-cultural approach must be applied to health care in general, since, in the absence of adequate mediators and interpreters, health professionals cannot report situations of high vulnerability such as trafficking, gender violence or other abuses.

Health care must be guaranteed from the very beginning of the process, especially in the case of VGs among the FDP. This is the case of pregnant women, they must be treated as soon as possible, especially if they wish to abort so that they are able to meet the deadlines.

Gender related policy recommendations:

- It is urgent to modify the Geneva Convention to expressly include persecution based on gender as grounds for asylum. As there was already a modification in the 1967 protocol, it can be modified again, it is a matter of political will.
- The two 2009 UNHCR guidelines are insufficient because protection is linked to indeterminate legal concepts that are subjectively interpretable by each country.
- Women must leave the protection linked to reason 5: Women are not a specific social group, because then, we would understand that normality is that the dominant group is men.
- We urge UNHCR to implement protocols with a gender perspective. Guidelines that reflect the diversity of gender-based violence are needed. The realities of each violence should be personalised, e.g. violence due to trafficking is not the same as violence due to not wanting to wear the veil. In this way, attention strategies could be better adapted.
- International law does not support an international convention on rape. There is no specific convention in which the Law defines what rape is. Then, the jurists do not have tools in International Law since this concept is not defined there. It always has to be connected with other crimes. For example, raping women is not considered a crime against Humanity, but they have to do something else to women.
- The Law must establish clear protocols for the protection of refugee women who have suffered violence.
- Collecting information on women who request international protection for reasons of gender and improve the social care for the group. The people who serve them, mostly men, have no training in gender perspective. There is also a lack of training in the field of intersectionality: women, racialised, lesbian...
- Generate public policies and mechanisms that include the gender and the intersectionality perspective.

3.3 Successful practices

In the United Kingdom, there is a decalogue of good practices of symbiosis between public administration and civil society organisations for the reception of forced migrants. Its application in other countries would improve the attention and inclusion of FDP in several aspects, as recommended by the experts of the Spanish ARU.

In Spain, there are examples of good practices in the reception of small groups within VGs with specialised social care (trafficking victims, elderly people, or mentally ill people). Nowadays, these good practices are at risk because the model of macro-reception centres is being encouraged. The recommendation is that these specific resources should be maintained for VGs among the FDP: small care centres that are leaders in welcoming a specific profile, for

example, sub-Saharan women seeking asylum (many of them with children). According to the Spanish ARU, this is the model that really works. More pilot projects of this type should be carried out to continue improving, with greater coordination by the public administration. It is not necessary to consider only the cost, a short-term concept that makes dependency and vulnerability chronic, since it does not consider the long-term costs if the system fails. We also recommend talking about public investment and not public spending when referring to displaced people.

Regarding entrepreneurship, “Maletas de Cartón” [Cardboard Suitcases] is an association that, among other areas of action, offers support to refugee entrepreneurs. As it was considered for the co-design of the Spanish TAIS, it is recommended to invest in programs that allow labour autonomy and decent work for forced migrants, taking advantage of their previous training, skills, and work experience.

To help with the inclusion in the host society, there are organisations in Spain that are developing a mentoring-type accompaniment. Volunteers who guide in aspects that professionals do not reach due to workload, but without occupying the professional's space. An example of this is the association “Sobre los márgenes” [On the margins]. These types of initiatives are carried out also in ACCEM organisation: where people from the host society make migrant friends, share leisure activities, and provide support in daily tasks. Thanks to this mentoring from ACCEM, a group of Syrian women has developed a small business, and other people have created a consumer group.

“CON-VIVIENDO, a process of inclusion of refugees in the municipalities of the Community of Madrid” as well as “Relational volunteer model”, both by the Spanish Commission for Refugee Aid (CEAR), are programs with similar networking purposes between asylum seekers and Spanish nationals by means of the promotion of intercultural and neighbourhood relations.

The European Nightingale project (<http://www.projecterossinyol.org/?lang=en>) includes universities and schools from all over Europe. It is an innovative and integrated network of practical and dynamic relationships between university students and schoolchildren of foreign origin.

Another example of work in settling down is developed by the NGO Luz Azul (<https://luzazulong.org/>). During the holidays, migrant minors and former migrant minors live together with Spanish citizens. Other examples are Befriending Project (Spanish Committee of UNHCR and Rescate Internacional NGO), GAUEAN (developed by Ekaitz Taldea networking with Fundación Harribide and Suspergintza Elkarte), Refugees Welcome, and the Intercultural Coexistence Service in Neighbourhoods (La Rueca Association).

We recommend investing in this type of innovative inclusion policies, as it is already done in some European countries, because it has been demonstrated that they favour inclusion. Community work and the creation of networks of belonging are especially recommended for VGs, since when the asylum application processes end, the organisations can no longer provide support. The feeling of identity and belonging is also favoured. With the pandemic, it has become even more important to have a support network.

Another interesting practice is Mejía Lequerica Shelter in Madrid, which serves mainly asylum seekers but also vulnerable migrants who have been left out of the asylum system for refugees. It is necessary to guarantee resources also for people suddenly finding themselves in an irregular situation if the application processes are lengthened or if the asylum is denied.

It is also important to empower VGs as in “Encounter Women Migrated from Getxo”. These workshops of encounter and training for migrated women try to offer a space of individual and collective learning in which they can reflect

on their position, the resistance and struggles they have faced, with special emphasis in their migratory story and in the reality they face in the new society.

Finally, by means of the practice “Solidarity of Responsibilities in the International Protection of Vulnerable Collectives”, La Merced Migraciones Foundation has detected and addressed the following needs, that could also be considered as policy recommendations:

- Work in coordination to identify the roles and responsibilities of the actors involved in the reception and inclusion processes.
- Reflect on the methodology and intervention with specific groups to ensure the protection of VGs.
- Solve the lack of specific resources for social care to minors, and LGBTQI+ asylum applicants.
- Improve the analysis of asylum applications from an age and a gender approach.
- Improve the quality of the asylum procedure regarding interviews with an adequate analysis of the mental health of the asylum seekers.
- Incorporate the cultural and social baggage of the asylum seekers and implement evaluation procedures that incorporate their vision.
- Develop training and exchange spaces among NGOs that develop programs within the framework of international protection, that will allow to exchange innovative and effective models of attention and inclusion.
- Apply a childhood and gender approach in the design of programs.
- Provide training for the identification and specific attention of the needs of LGBTQI+ asylum seekers.

3.4 Summary

The analysis of micro, meso and macro levels of socio-ecological models shows a big picture about how Spanish government, institutions, organisations and other actors are addressing the inclusion of VGs among FDP. The analysis shows three relevant general factors that determine social exclusion: ignorance on how vulnerability is constructed, lack of resources, and the absence of political will. The lack of knowledge about how the vulnerability is built does not help to protect those who suffer this condition. The common knowledge put the focus on the people who experience the vulnerability and not on the interaction between people and their environment. A second element is the lack of true political will to support those FDP in many cases. Even when the commitment reached is to safeguard their fundamental rights, often the time and resources allocated to the inclusion of VGs among the FDP are not sufficient, because finally they cannot get out of that vulnerability. Besides these general factors, there are specific issues and recommendations related to inclusion and integration in certain aspects that are discussed next.

During the asylum application process, the specific needs of the most vulnerable groups regarding mental health care, trauma, gender violence, disabilities and other individual, intrafamily or community factors should be considered. This is the beginning of the social exclusion they will suffer if the attention does not tackle those issues. To void it, when defining the different VGs that apply for international protection, the actors need to adopt an intersectional approach that considers the forms of oppression suffered, including the gender perspective. It is also necessary to adapt the times of the social care and inclusion processes of VGs to their greater needs.

Regarding economic factors, when assistance ends, there are many FDP who have not yet been able to be economically autonomous. It would be necessary to implement more help with language and improve the offer of free courses to work. In addition, the FDP ignores her/his own rights and possible help. Complete information should be offered to asylum seekers about aid and subsidies to which they are eligible. Also, it would be necessary to improve FDP's labour insertion.

With the aim of improving the labour conditions and insertion, the authorisation to work should be accelerated. Moreover, jobs should not be incompatible with social aid and subsidies until the former do not provide sufficient remuneration and are full-time. It is also necessary to work on employability and facilitate hiring FDP. Adapting the educational training of the FDP to the labour offer would increase their opportunities of getting a job. From the side of actions related to potential employers and other workers, it would be necessary to carry out information campaigns about the situation of the FDP and involve the trade unions. Positive discrimination actions could be applied, such as reserving a quota to hire.

Another difficulty for FDP is finding housing. Many landlords are reluctant to hire with FDP due to misconceptions and wrong information about them. Public information campaigns should be carried out on what the "Red Card" and the Foreign Resident Identification Number are, as well as reserving public housing from the Administration.

Guaranteeing access to education is key when talking about social inclusion of VGs. The problems start at the arrival, since educational centres tend to lack transitional classrooms or specialised support, which makes that many students do not adapt and often repeat a year, or keep adaptation problems over the years. There are also problems in the access to higher education, which is not mandatory and therefore where support fades. They need this support since they cannot spend 4 years studying if their survival is not guaranteed. First, a curricular adaptation is necessary at university, which does not yet exist, so that the VG among FDP could have better access and success at university. In addition, the processes of homologation of academic degrees take long and are expensive. Validation of studies should be facilitated to ensure a better social inclusion, for instance with advisors, no fees and shorter processes.

Regarding socio-sanitary factors, free and universal healthcare should be guaranteed by the Administrations, and it should include the cross-cultural approach. Moreover, information campaigns in health centres are needed, so that administrative staff are aware of the "Red Card" and that refugees do not have problems with health care. It is also necessary to improve training because international protection applicants did not reach municipal services.

As for gender, it is urgent to modify the Geneva Convention to expressly include persecution based on gender as grounds for asylum. As there was already a modification in the 1967 protocol, it can be modified again, so it is a matter of political will.

In general, there is a widespread problem of lack of information. For instance, regarding the situation of FDP and the possibilities of working with them, for instance the meaning of the Red Card. Information campaign need to be run regarding FDP-related issues.

A general issue underlying many of these problem is the budget of these services. In general. budgets need to be increased so that social care can be tailored to the profile of asylum seekers and their specific needs. This should be considered as a medium or long term investment instead of a short-time cost. At the end, the cost of failed inclusion is higher than that of suitable actions.

4 Policy brief summarising the main results and findings of the project for stakeholders from University of Helsinki (Finland)

4.1 Vulnerability

In this policy brief, vulnerability refers to a situation determined by both contextual conditions and individual features and capabilities. Vulnerability not only indicates one's exposure to potential harms but refers to the reduced capacity to cope with the harms as well. Even though vulnerability is a universal human condition, the level of vulnerability tends to change according to contextual and situational factors. In Finland, asylum seekers constitute a group with an increased risk of being exposed to vulnerabilities. This is partly because their agency is limited in several ways and many of them, particularly young men, suffer from severe stigmatisation. Consequently, in this policy brief, the focus is on the alleviation of asylum seekers' vulnerabilities within the Finnish reception system. All arguments below draw from research work conducted during RAISD-project in 2019-2022.

4.1.1 On micro-level. Considerations about personal conditions and features

In Finland, different asylum seekers are treated in different ways depending on their individual features and the social categories they are associated with. In the legislative and practical levels, asylum seekers who are recognised as unaccompanied minors and victims of human trafficking are treated as vulnerable. Consequently, they are supported with various special services and rights. The group-based and static definition of vulnerability in the legislative discourse defines most asylum seekers as non-vulnerable. However, there are numerous vulnerabilities among asylum seekers that have not been recognised. Throughout the empirical work in the Finnish sub-project, we focused on the two previously misrecognised groups that also suffer from vulnerabilities: young asylum-seeking men and parents of small children.

Young asylum-seeking men in their early twenties have constituted the largest group of asylum seekers in Finland and in Northern Europe in general. Instead of seeing young men as vulnerable or at risk for vulnerability, they are often discriminated and considered as a suspicious and even dangerous category. However, most asylum-seeking young men lack the support of their families and wider communities in the new and exclusive surroundings. Moreover, in the legislation and in the reception system, after allegedly turning 18, they are treated as adults and accordingly receive little support. Their dispersed families might expect them to be able to settle in Finland and provide for them rapidly. At the same time, their rights in Finland are severely limited, including their access to education and labour market. Consequently, young men with low education and poor skills in relevant languages (Finnish, Swedish and English) are often in a difficult position.

In addition to young men, we focused on asylum-seeking parents with small children as an example of a large group suffering from unsatisfied needs in the Finnish context. Many parents aim to establish their position rather rapidly in a new society to be able to support their children in best possible ways. However, asylum-seeking parents have had poor chances to reach this goal. Most children below school age have not had the right in municipal day care services. For particularly single parents, this has meant inability to work or educate themselves. In a more fundamental level, parents suffering from traumas or poor mental health have had difficulties in coping with the stress of everyday life in Finland. Moreover, their children have missed the opportunity to stability and interaction with their Finnish-speaking peers and access to Finnish education system.

The experiences of certain misrecognised sub-groups of asylum seekers and their vulnerabilities illustrate the deficiencies of Finnish reception system on a more general level. While some small sub-groups and their needs are

recognised (e.g., unaccompanied youth), the needs and vulnerabilities of the majority remain unrecognised, or they are easily defined as an undeserving or even a dangerous category of people.

4.1.2 On meso-level. Interrelationships in the environments in Finland

In Finland, all asylum seekers are provided minimum level of services and benefits. In an international level, these services and benefits are generous. However, in relation to surrounding communities, asylum seekers need to cope with the minimum level of living standard. Overall, the Finnish reception system tends to isolate asylum seekers from the institutions and communities of the mainstream society: Asylum seeker's access to education, public services, and their right to work is highly limited. Further, most reception centres are in peripheral areas in rural or peri-urban locations. The Finnish reception system is more about security and confinement than wellbeing and inclusion. The confining structure of the reception system leaves asylum seekers with special needs in an underserved position. This concerns particularly those with limited language skills, educational competences, social networks, and health-related problems.

Reception centres provide diverse services which are designed to support the early integration of asylum seekers. These services include language tuition and work activities. However, both take place within reception centres. According to asylum seekers, language tuition remains on a basic level and is repetitive. Opportunities for development are limited. Further, work activities equal to maintenance of the reception centre premises and include less counselling and opportunities to familiarise oneself with work environments outside reception centres. As a result of limitations in integrative services within the reception system and their precarious position in the Finnish labour market in general, asylum seekers are highly susceptible to exploitation by employers.

Therefore, and particularly in conditions in which asylum processes are protracted, asylum seekers would benefit from reforms in reception services. More effort could be invested in childcare services, counselling in relation to education and work and multilingual information on local possibilities.

4.1.3 On macro-level: macro-policies, culture, economic issues, believes, etc.

On a general level, asylum seekers constitute a stigmatised category of people. Particularly young male asylum seekers from Arab and African countries are often treated as undeserving refugees. The recent flow of Ukrainian people fleeing their homes due to invasion of the Russian army has revealed the ethnic hierarchies in accepting refugees. After early May 2022, we have witnessed rapid and unprecedented changes concerning the European reception system and asylum policies. A temporary residence permit is granted to all Ukrainian citizens. Moreover, according to Finnish media coverage, some changes have already taken place in the context of the reception system. New reception centres have been established in locations closer to services and urban centres, municipalities have been highly active in securing education and day care for children soon after arrival. Ukrainian people are more frequently accommodated in private apartments instead of institutional housing. Even a pet-friendly reception centre has been set up.

In the political rhetoric, representatives of all parties use positive tone when talking about the people fleeing from Ukraine. This is exceptional in the political discourses on immigration. Consequently, Ukrainian citizens will probably have a better start in accommodating themselves in Finland than previous refugees and asylum seekers. Despite the ethnic hierarchies and the injustice toward asylum seekers who have been confined in the reception system for years, it is possible that the war in Ukraine will eventually have positive outcomes for all asylum seekers. Time will tell whether the isolating features of the reception system will be replaced by investments in inclusion and wellbeing.

In any case, the current situation with Ukrainian refugees provides an important lesson from the perspective of Finnish and European reception of refugees and asylum seekers: The way people are treated is mostly about political will. If there is a will, there seems to be several ways in considering the needs and potential vulnerabilities of forcibly displaced population. In the light of our research before the current crisis, asylum seekers from other regions would also benefit greatly from similar reception.

4.2 *Issues of diversity*

The Finnish Constitution, Equality Act and legislation concerning refugee and asylum-seeking populations, provide tools for considering diversities such as gender, ethnicity, religion, sexuality, and disabilities. However, a solid legislation does not mean that there would be no discrimination at the institutional level and in daily life. Together with other institutions, the Finnish reception system is not free of discrimination based on the above identity categories. However, according to our empirical findings, there are even more relevant categories of vulnerability than those primarily considered in the legislation.

Finland's peripheral location and European Union's strict immigration policies have had important consequences. Young and physically fit men from middle-class backgrounds who are the most able to take the dangerous, expensive, and long journey to Finland constitute the predominant category of asylum seekers in Finland. This means that groups most susceptible to discrimination are underrepresented among asylum seekers in Finland. Unlike women and children, young men are rarely seen as vulnerable in the public discourse. Moreover, it is often the case that young men themselves wish not to present themselves as susceptible to vulnerabilities or discrimination, even though in many cases they would benefit from accepting help and support.

Consequently, instead of diversity in the traditional or legislative sense, the focus has been on previously misrecognised categories of vulnerability in the context of the Finnish reception system. Our empirically supported choice has been to focus on young men and parents of small children. As a result of our work, as with the notion of vulnerability, we recommend analysing the notion of diversity in a context sensitive manner as well without predetermined assumptions about the most relevant categories. This is not to deny the importance of other categories such as ethnicity and sexuality. As the war in Ukraine has shown, the ethnicity of potential refugees matters even at the systemic level. Moreover, it is likely that, for instance, homosexual men face various forms of harassment and even violence in Finnish reception centres. Finally, there is empirical evidence to support the idea that religion and demarcations between Christianity and Islam might lead into discrimination as well. Turning into Christianity might open some doors in the Finnish society, but it might also lead into experienced harassment in reception centre communities.

4.3 *Successful practices*

Finnish reception services tend to isolate asylum seekers from the surrounding society and communities. The main function of the system is to confine and control asylum seekers while their applications are processed. Since the processes can take several years, it would be wise to invest more effort on helping asylum seekers to build connections to surrounding communities and institutions.

Consequently, there need to be more services focusing on labour market and education counselling. Currently, these types of services are almost absent in the reception centres. In addition to counselling and promoting institutional attachments, there is a need to develop translocal methods of online support and volunteer work in reception centres located peripheral areas. In addition to educational and work opportunities, also leisure activities and

volunteer support are often lacking in the areas in which asylum seekers are located. Due to the war in Ukraine, societal atmosphere is currently favourable toward positive changes in the reception system.

As for more detailed recommendations, two things are worth mentioning here. First, asylum-seeking families' right to early childhood education and care services should be granted in the national legislation. If this is not possible, municipalities should ensure asylum-seeking children's access to public day-care services. Currently, most asylum-seeking children have no right to municipal day-care services. Moreover, reception centres are not obligated to provide child-care services and the level of provided activities varies between the centres. For many families, this situation aggravates problems in a very stressful situation. Parents' abilities to work or educate themselves and rest are highly limited. Moreover, children miss structured activities, professional support in their development and learning, and are separated from their Finnish-speaking peers. Several children must start their school careers without any socialisation to the Finnish educational system and language tuition.

Second, a more coherent and systematic body of online methods need to be developed in the work with asylum seekers. Considering that Finnish reception centres are often located in peripheral areas, online methods and support might have a major impact. Voluntary workers, educators, legal support, and various face-to-face services are rarely available in the living spheres of many asylum seekers. A key development would be to relocate the reception centres into more central areas, but this type of development is unlikely to happen soon. For this reason, Immigration Service and Red Cross could appoint a person responsible for developing and designing online support practices. At the present time, not enough resources are available for developing online work. In addition to providing support to asylum seekers, online channels could be used to share multilingual information among asylum seekers. Currently, information is shared in a traditional form in bulletin boards in the offices of reception centres. Those asylum seekers who have few reasons to visit the offices, might miss some of the relevant information.

4.4 Summary

When considering the reception of asylum seekers in the European Union, the most pressing issue is related to ideologies and orientations, not some small-scale practices. From the perspective of asylum seekers, the primary aim of reception should be inclusion and integration, not confinement and security. At best, reception of asylum seekers would promote the autonomy of people and foster their capacities in the receiving societies. In the long run and from the perspective of economy, this would very likely turn into a more productive strategy than the current situation.

Furthermore, the concept of vulnerability should be redefined in the legislation as well as in the public discourse. Very often, the dominant idea on vulnerability relies on essentialist notions of certain groups of people. Definitions of vulnerability tend to resort to the 'women-and-children' discourse. The dominant discourse on vulnerability is harmful to both women and children and to men as well by victimizing women and children and denying their agency while men are seen as potential security risks. Moreover, the dominant discourse reinforces the distinction between deserving and undeserving refugees and, by doing so, maintains racism against asylum-seeking men across European countries.

Consequently, the notion of vulnerability needs to be seen as contextual and situational. The same person can be resilient in one context/situation and vulnerable in some other. Also, young men can be vulnerable in certain conditions and situations. Young men themselves would benefit from being able to present them as vulnerable instead of performing traditional masculinities. Instead of only listing vulnerable groups, global organisations, such

as European Union, need to approach vulnerability in more sensitive manners and see the differences between various regions, contexts, and situations.

5 Policy brief summarising the main results and findings of the project for stakeholders from Lebanese International University (Lebanon)

5.1 Vulnerability

5.1.1 On micro-level. Considerations about personal conditions and features

Covid-19 pandemic has exacerbated old vulnerabilities while steadily increasing the intensity of these realities among vulnerable groups, and triggering a wide range of mental health conditions, which may lead long-term psychosocial consequences. Fear of deportation or eviction, discrimination, as well as loss or reduced livelihoods remain major sources of psychosocial distress according to the current situation. Additionally, these fears have laid the foundation for negative social reactions, including but not limited to panic, stigma, and discrimination in the communities. Moreover, most vulnerable people are exhibiting high levels of psychological distress. This includes individuals and families with pre-existing mental health conditions or substance abuse issues.

Syrian refugees in Lebanon are subject to several stressors which are the direct result of traumatic events in conflict situations or the daily hurdles being a refugee. The mere fact of struggling to uphold essential living conditions as well as living through the uncertainty about their legal standing and livelihood are but the tip of the iceberg of everyday challenges for Syrian refugee communities. War-related traumas, coupled with daily stressors have major implications upon the long-term psychosocial well-being of refugees. Social distress, cognitive problems, chronic pain, and post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) are typical documented reactions from prolonged stress situations among refugees in Lebanon. Social Educational Academic Development (SEAD) was a small step to help support mental health services to elevate the living standards of displaced Syrians across Lebanon. Despite the need for mental health and psychosocial support being alarmingly high and options in remote areas of Lebanon where vulnerable Syrians are at mass, there is little or no support from any grass root organisation to support.

Women:

There is a clear lack of data on Syrian women refugees in Lebanon. It is very important to conduct further needs assessments that should focus on groups such as women's spouses, community leaders, local community-based women groups, and religious based organisations to clarify the risks that vulnerable women face. In other words, an understanding of the ways that vulnerable women's health, mental and social problems differ from local Lebanese counterparts. This in turn can help policymakers and relevant providers to address such specific needs.

Many vulnerable women are reluctant to speak about their issues. There is an inhibition mainly due to patriarchal and cultural elements among Syrian refugees, which creates difficulties for all women. A thorough needs assessment is a good place to start to understand the landscape of Syrian women's and other vulnerable groups' needs. In this regard, one policy recommendation should aim at providing a medium that would allow vulnerable women more control or autonomy over their lives.

Youth:

Syrian refugees are highly concentrated in peripheral regions and some of the poorest areas of the country, mainly the North, the South and Beqaa. A snapshot of the living conditions and developmental status of those three regions that host a fair number of Syrian refugees reveals elevated poverty rates, high levels of illiteracy, low educational attainment, low incomes, seasonality of jobs, and inexistent social protection mechanisms.

A policy recommendation to policy makers is to coordinate with international agencies to facilitate flexible regulations allowing vulnerable young people without a residence permit to sit for Lebanese official exams and enrol in schools. In addition, priority should also be placed to allow such vulnerable group access technical and vocational training linked to job opportunities. In working such end, key target groups such as youth with representation from different sub-segments and young influencers (e.g., parents, caregivers, and teachers) should also be involved.

5.1.2 On meso-level. Interrelationships in the environments in Lebanon

The conflict in Syria – combined with internal political instability – has had negative repercussions on the economy and the labour market at different levels. Given the fragility of the security situation, and the closure of Syrian borders – the only route exit trade for Lebanon, private investments have stalled, and the trade deficit has largely expanded. The two most important sectors – tourism and real estate– have been especially affected. The already large fiscal deficit has widened even more due to lower revenues combined with rising government expenditures. Government expenditures have been rising to meet the increasing demand for public services, including education, health, electricity, water supply, solid waste management and transportation; revenues have decreased due to disturbed trade activity, lower economic activity, and a loss in consumer confidence.

Most Syrian refugees are living in hard socio-economic conditions with limited livelihood options and few connections or acquaintances; they have scant means of self-reliance, especially female-headed households who make up a good share of the refugee population. Refugees' limited financial resources are usually spent on accommodation, often in poor conditions.

Syrian refugees are obliged to pay high prices for small shelters, share apartments with more families or, for those who cannot afford the rents, move to Palestinian camps, abandoned buildings or tented settlements. Symptomatically, the rise of infectious diseases and scabies indicate the kind of deficient living conditions that certain segments of the Syrian refugee population have been forced to endure. It is important to note that the central Government prohibited any intervention for the enhancement of tent settlements across the country under a policy that hinders the creation of camps for Syrian refugees in Lebanon. As a result, the demand for shelter has exceeded supply in many parts of the country with more than 60 per cent of Syrian refugees living in rented accommodation.

The Ministry of Education and Higher Education (MEHE) facilitated access to education for Syrian refugees to all public schools. However, both students and schools continue to face significant challenges. Although classrooms in the public Government schools in Lebanon are generally not overcrowded and the ratio of students to teachers is the lowest in public schools, the high concentration of Syrian refugees in host communities in North and Bekaa has led to the overcrowding of schools that were previously under-populated. Syrian refugee students face several obstacles that not only hinder their access to education (for example, transportation costs and discrimination), but also affect their ability to learn in school, such as differences between the curricula and language (French or English are the languages of instruction for most school subjects).

Syrian refugees have access to primary healthcare services that are provided for free by public dispensaries of the Ministry of Social Affairs and the Ministry of Public Health (MoPH), in addition to services provided by humanitarian international organisations and local NGOs. However, these services seem to be insufficient and are unable to accommodate the additional significant increase of demand – especially in terms of reproductive health. Syrian refugee children in Lebanon can also obtain vaccination against several diseases, such as measles and polio, provided at national primary health care facilities and through vaccination campaigns organised by the MoPH. These services, however, are generally limited to registered refugees, rendering unregistered refugees with very limited healthcare

support. Even though other healthcare costs, such as hospitalisation, are subsidised by international agencies (mainly UNHCR), many refugees are still unable to afford the remaining costs.

Some 90 percent of Syrian refugee households in Lebanon have no or only one family member generating income, either through formal or informal channels. According to Lebanese labour law, Syrian refugees are barred from employment in all but three sectors: agriculture, cleaning, and construction. Furthermore, Lebanese authorities have long refrained from strictly enforcing relevant laws, due to a combination of limited capacities and a tacit recognition of the negative consequences that such enforcement would have for both Syrian refugees and the Lebanese economy.

A lack of legal residency and other civil documentation is both a driver and an effect of the economic vulnerability of Syrian refugees in Lebanon. The more desperate a family's economic situation is, the less likely is that they will be able to afford processing fees, transport cost, or lost wages required to obtain or renew their documentations. The prolonged legal vulnerability of Syrian refugees has critical implications. Squeezed among economic pressures, legal vulnerability, and limited access to services, refugees also report being deeply affected by the increasingly hostile social climate in Lebanon. A combination of harassment, disrespect, and the all-out violence against Syrians compounds the alienation and homesickness of many refugees experience.

5.1.3 On macro-level: macro-policies, culture, economic issues, believes, etc.

Aid for the Syria refugee crisis in Lebanon is precipitously decreasing as donor fatigue worsens, public attention wanes, and anti-refugee sentiment grows. Violence against refugees has been steadily becoming more common and more gruesome, most notably after the blaze of war in Aarsal. 'Revenge' attacks for the actions of groups like the Islamic State or Jabhat al-Nusra, or for isolated crimes by Syrian individuals, that target refugees, their homes, and their property are becoming increasingly frequent. It is worth noting that the Islamic State militant responsible for the beheadings of two Lebanese Armed Forces soldiers, an act that spurred a large part of these 'revenge attacks' was Lebanese, not Syrian. Reports of refugee camps being set alight, drive-by shootings, and attacks against refugees by racist mobs are now a daily feature of Lebanese news broadcasts, and some have begun to (accurately) describe these events as 'pogroms'. In addition to collective punishment, misdirected rage, and dehumanisation, these attacks are also motivated by the widely held belief that Syrian refugees are largely responsible for most of Lebanon's ailments. The Lebanese have traditionally been masters at projecting and diverting blame onto others. Syrian refugees are being scapegoated for a plethora of issues including, but not limited to, electricity and water shortages, the uptick in crime, traffic jams and accidents, inflation, and terrorist attacks.

The dehumanisation of the Syrian refugee in the minds of most Lebanese has resulted in acts of immeasurable cruelty. Two particular incidents made headlines after videos taken by the perpetrators spread on social media. The first video showed Lebanese parents prodding their toddler to beat a cowering Syrian child with a wooden stick. The second video shows a knife-wielding Lebanese man threatening to behead three sobbing Syrian children, while accusing them of belonging to the Islamic State.

Drawing upon these two incidents one can conceptualise the nature of the disease that ails Lebanese society, of which these are only two of many symptoms.

Suspending all laws which inter alia stipulate punishments for illegal entry and breaking terms of residency visas. The absence of any initiative to organise the Syrian refugees' presence in Lebanon, in that official policy contains no measures to regulate such presence. As for encouraging refugees to leave Lebanon, we witness a similar approach

in proactive measures towards reducing the number of “displaced persons” resident in Lebanon. The government has softened its discourse in this regard, talking about the need to “encourage Syrian displaced persons to return to their country or to other countries, by all possible means”. The word “encourage” is highly suggestive in this context and can only be understood as an indicator of the government’s desire to use non-repressive measures in implementing policies. More precisely, it seems that the government is urging at political level for these refugees to voluntarily leave Lebanon.

The shortfall in funding affects all societal sectors. Support for relief and basic needs receded from its peak in 2015 and 2016, with an overall funding trend towards development aid as opposed to emergency relief. Even for funding commitments made, it is unclear how such funds are to be disbursed and actually reach targeted beneficiaries. A systemic lack of accountability and transparency in tracking extends from donor states and institutions to the Lebanese ministries that are supposed to oversee the response and down to the level of service providers.

The Minister of Energy (now Minister of Foreign Affairs) and MP for the Free Patriotic Movement Gibran Bassil, made a similar point in 2013 when he said of the influx of Syrian refugees, "what is happening is organised crime carried out by Lebanese and foreign officials to change the country's demography". This fixation on sectarian and demographic balance and on national identity has been a feature of right-wing rhetoric since before the Lebanese Civil War, when it was directed against Palestinian, rather than Syrian refugees.

Racism against Syrian nationals in Lebanon cannot be understood outside of its historic and economic context. The proliferation of anti-Syrian sentiment in Lebanese society already was a cause for concern and condemnation well before the beginning of the Syrian uprising and the subsequent influx of refugees. For decades, the demonym ‘Syrian’ has been employed to insult, denoting vulgarity, low social and economic status, bad taste, poor hygiene, etc. Racially motivated attacks against Syrian nationals aren’t without precedent either. In 2005, Syrian workers in Lebanon were the victims of (often fatal) attacks motivated by the suspected culpability of the Syrian government in former Lebanese Prime Minister Rafic al-Hariri’s assassination.

In 2017 Human Rights Watch released a report investigating the extent to which donor funding for the education sector in Lebanon’s crisis response is opaque, unearthing a lack of consistent and timely reporting by donors, missing or unspecific information about the projects donors are funding and their timing, and inconsistent information about overall targets and goals. These structural challenges about funding transparency are not confined to the education sector, but instead are mirrored across other sectors.

Compounding the reduction in aid, Lebanese authorities have taken steps to further restrict the livelihoods opportunities for Syrian refugees.

Recently issued statements by the head of Lebanon’s General Security directorate (GSO), claims that nearly 90,000 Syrian refugees returned to Syria from Lebanon in 2018. The UNHCR, on the other hand, has confirmed 16,700 cases of return in 2018. While the GSO figure has not been verified and is highly likely to be inflated, the UNHCR figure is a low estimate, since it reflects only cases of return that can be verified through household visits or family member interviews, and UNHCR lacks full access to Syria. Aside from these disputed return statistics, a lack of clarity extends across the entire return landscape in Lebanon.

Both the UN, major EU donor states, and the Lebanese political leaders all use similar terms to describe the appropriate standards for returns to Syria. These actors often employ terms such as ‘voluntary’, ‘safe’, and ‘dignified’ when speaking about refugee returns, but they are part of wildly divergent arguments about return. For the UN and

the EU, 'safety' means that returning to Syria must be linked to credible security guarantees for returnees, with the understanding that safety is about more than the absence of an outright war. Rather, safety extends to political, legal, social, and economic concerns.

After eleven years of dealing with the refugee crisis, Lebanon does not have a clear national strategy to systematically and efficiently respond to it. In effect, the municipalities have had shouldered such a burden given the insufficiency of aid that can be attributed to donor fatigue.

It is recommended that an official communication channel should be established between the Lebanese national government and the local authorities to respond to the crisis. Whereby more standardised responses ought to be left for municipalities responsible for absorbing and dealing with the refugees and other vulnerable groups by providing them with basic needs.

As international agencies and donors realise the importance of municipalities as authoritative local bodies and provide them with more support, management would improve and tensions between host populations and vulnerable groups would be reduced.

Climate:

There will be a huge scope on climate change that will result in direct and indirect human health impacts causing different damages. The direct effects result from changing temperatures that trigger the outbreak of infectious diseases; from heat waves that can increase morbidity and mortality; and other extreme weather events and their consequences such as floods, storms, and massive fires, which can cause an increase in the number of casualties.

The indirect effects of climate change on human health include droughts and floods affecting agriculture and leading to malnutrition; scarcity of clean water, which widely impairs hygienic conditions; and migration due to changing environments, which makes humans vulnerable to a whole host of diseases.

Higher temperatures may lead to alterations in the geographic range (latitude and altitude) and seasonality of certain infectious diseases including vector-borne infections and food-borne infections which peak in the warmer months, malnutrition risk and certain rodent-borne diseases are associated with flooding as this has increased lately in Lebanon in the last 3 years.

Water and sanitation are primary drivers of public health or the consequences to the battle against certain communicable diseases would remain rising with fear.

Most of the water distribution networks are old, subject to periodic cuts and present a high risk of contamination in areas where there is no sewerage network. People are exposed to water-borne diseases because of the lack of pressure in the distribution network when water is cut. This cut allows wastewater to pollute the freshwater network.

Lebanon is still in the epidemiological transition phase that started two decades ago, whereby infectious and communicable diseases remain endemic with an increase in the prevalence of non-communicable and degenerative diseases. In fact, Lebanon still reports endemic diseases such as tuberculosis, seasonal diarrhoea, and zoonotic diseases.

Human health would be adversely affected by higher temperatures and increased risk of floods.

It is imminent that the most vulnerable displaced people in Lebanon are the most likely impacts of climate change on human health in Lebanon. It would lead to a huge future gap between what currently is and the future variation in the demographic, socio-economic and technological driving forces of the country- the sensitivity, adaptive capacity, and vulnerability of vulnerable hotspots under socio-economic and climate change.

5.2 Issues of diversity

Vulnerable groups among the FDP face barriers that directly affect their ability to integrate into the host country. Some of these societal barriers often include discriminatory social norms and policies that lead to stigma, cultural and religious considerations, and language barriers.

Such policy consideration highlights the importance of age, and gender as well as sexual orientation, gender identity, disability, or belonging to a minority group as issues of diversity. It must be recognised that these traits play a critical role in determining a person's opportunities, capacities, needs and risks.

Women:

- We provide the following recommendations for women:
- Equal representation and influence of women in community leadership and management structures.
- Access to safe and sustainable livelihoods opportunities.
- Sexual and gender-based violence (SGBV) prevention and response.
- Affordable, accessible, and adequate sexual and reproductive health services.

Older people:

We provide the following recommendations for older people:

- Adequate family and community support structures.
- Access to pension benefits and livelihoods opportunities.
- Prevention of, and response to, SGBV, and elder abuse.
- Access to health services.

Children:

We provide the following recommendations for children:

- Safe access to quality education.
- Protection from abuse, neglect, violence, and exploitation.
- Adequate protection and solutions for unaccompanied and separated children.
- Universal birth registration.

Youth:

We provide the following recommendations for young FDP:

- Safe and affordable access to quality education, especially post-primary, non-formal and accelerated learning opportunities.
- Meaningful participation and representation in decision-making processes.
- Support for emotional, psychological, and spiritual wellbeing.

- Access to vocational training and sustainable livelihood opportunities.

People with disabilities:

Vulnerable people are facing serious risks because of multiple and complex unmet needs, which cross both medical and social dimensions. There is, however, a tendency to refer most persons with disabilities to service providers for health, rehabilitation and provision of aids and devices, sometimes failing to recognise other factors. These factors might include their children being out of school, living in substandard shelters, being single parents or care givers and single women with disabilities. Some specific situations require a more comprehensive and holistic protection assessment and referral to a variety of other non-health-related services. Health and rehabilitation service providers report that this results in a large number of referrals for persons with long standing disabilities that do not in fact require medical care or have a low priority for rehabilitation interventions. This may create inefficiency in an already overloaded system, and further delays in identifying and responding to persons deemed at high risk for protection.

LIU ARU members recognise that people with disabilities are a significant portion of their beneficiary population, and they have recommended that further training would support them to better assess vulnerability and risk factors and to better respond to protection concerns. In particular, facilitating more targeted action planning for interventions, including those which can be delivered directly by case managers (e.g., monitoring and counselling families) and referral to other agencies for more specialised specialised interventions.

Some Syrian refugees with new injuries and impairments do require specialised interventions, such as surgery and longer-term rehabilitation, to ensure their full and effective participation in society. Whilst local hospitals, NGOs and charities have been meeting the immediate medical needs of this group, they are now reaching full capacity as the number of wars injured. Due to resource limitations and the emergency nature of operations, health agencies are only able to provide limited urgent and life-saving services. In some cases, individuals pay for surgery and rehabilitation services that are not covered by other agencies. As a consequence, it puts further financial strain on such self-paying individuals and their families. Inpatient rehabilitation is very limited in time, and many persons with injuries and new impairments are discharged home with hardly any follow-up.

There are several families of persons with intellectual impairments facing extreme challenges and social isolation as refugees. In most cases, the families have had little guidance and support and they have therefore resorted to ad hoc coping strategies. Some are using physical and medical restraint to prevent family members from leaving the shelter and/or harming themselves and others. Stigma and fear of exploitation may also contribute to families hiding their relative, adding to the isolation of the individual. There are very few specialised services available in Lebanon for such families, highlighting again the important role that social workers from case management agencies must play in counselling, monitoring and linking to child protection protocols.

Ensuring quality education for Syrian refugees remains as a significant challenge with an estimated 80 percent of refugee children aged 6 to 17 currently out of school and in need of further support. Children with disabilities had not been attending school or other educational activities since arriving in Lebanon. Only a small number of children, those with vision and mild physical impairments, had been attending school in Syria, reflecting that children with disabilities are disproportionately denied their right to education in a variety of contexts and settings. Education of Lebanese children with disabilities is largely through Ministry of Social Affairs (MOSA)- funded private schools. MOSA social workers report that these schools are already at full capacity and many Lebanese children with disabilities find it difficult to access them. The Ministry of Education and Higher Education (MEHE) devolves decision making on

inclusion of children with disabilities in public schools to local directors “dependent on their capacity.” There are some small scale examples of NGOs working directly with public schools to support inclusion of selected children with disabilities, but to date this has mostly not happened.

The following two recommendations address key gaps in the current humanitarian response for persons with disabilities and may have strategic importance for inclusion in longer-term planning.

1. Recognise the needs of people with new impairments in longer-term response planning.

The lack of services for people with severe new impairments has resulted individuals being discharged home with limited support, posing significant protection concerns. The inclusion of community-based rehabilitation activities is a very positive step in addressing this gap. This model has the potential to deliver services to people with disabilities in the community, as well as promoting empowerment and inclusion in other community activities, such as livelihoods and education. There is a clear need, however, to determine the number of persons with impairments more precisely as the Syria conflict drags on. Whilst it may be unrealistic to fund all health and rehabilitation services at this stage in the humanitarian response, it is critical that any unmet needs are documented, and included in future regional response planning and funding purposes.

2. Pilot and evaluate guidelines for identifying risk and prioritizing the most vulnerable.

Many persons with disabilities and their families have complex protection issues crossing both medical and social sectors, which require timely comprehensive assessment, coordinated direct support and referral to multiple agencies. The identification and referral process for persons with disabilities can be strengthened through the provision of guidelines about identifying heightened risk and urgency for comprehensive assessment. Given the large number of persons with disabilities in the refugee community, prioritisation may be best based on multiple specific needs or compounding vulnerabilities. Hence, individuals with multiple and intersecting levels of discrimination are identified as being among the most vulnerable to be referred to case management agencies for full assessment, coordination, and follow-up. Likewise, this will prioritise the most vulnerable persons with disabilities and their families for humanitarian programs and financial assistance.

Key recommendations for other vulnerable groups:

The challenges and the gaps identified indicate the following policy recommendations:

- 1) Take specific measures in adjusting programs and working directly with women, to provide support to ease caretaking, household and livelihoods-related responsibilities that impede the participation of certain groups, particularly women, girls, boys, and young people, in areas such as education and community leadership.
- 2) Continue to ensure that community-based support mechanisms are strengthened to address social isolation, facilitate discussion on sensitive subjects, increase participation of marginalised groups, counter stigma and discrimination, and reduce risks of sexual and gender-based violence and other forms of violence and abuse.
- 3) Strengthen efforts to address the under-identification of marginalised and stigmatised groups, such as survivors of sexual and gender-based violence, the creation of safe spaces and improvements in data collection.
- 4) Given the psychological suffering and other public health and protection problems, such as substance abuse and gender-based violence, greater emphasis should be placed on exploring the resources and mechanisms that can be used to treat mental health and psychosocial problems that affect welfare of FPD.

5) Reinforce the implementation of and the reporting on accountability to persons of concern, particularly in the areas of communication and transparency, participation and inclusion, feedback and response mechanisms, and programme adaptation and learning.

5.3 Successful practices

On the one hand, highlight two examples of good practices among the ones that have been previously identified:

#	Practice	Target Vulnerable Group	Aim of the inclusion practice
1	WHO's Contribution to the Health Response: Main Projects	Vulnerable, displaced Syrians.	To reinforce quality primary and secondary health care, reinforcement of communicable diseases monitoring, early warning and response system, and equipping health facilities and supplying vaccines and medicines.
2	Enabling Job Resilience and Protecting Decent Work Conditions in Rural Communities Affected by the Syrian Refugee Crisis in Northern Lebanon	Rural employment, community development, local economic development, agricultural development, agriculture, refugees.	To create productive employment through local economic development and sustainable enterprises in northern Lebanese communities affected by the Syrian refugee crisis.

On the other hand, community centres, which are established in the MOSA facilities (called Social Development Centres) or separately by NGOs, are rapidly becoming a hallmark of the Syrian refugee response in Lebanon. A wide variety of services, including women's protection and empowerment, child-friendly spaces, accelerated learning programs and vocational training activities, are currently delivered through these centres. A large network of NGO outreach workers and refugee outreach volunteers is being developed to share information about these centres and the available services. Very few persons with disabilities and their care givers are accessing these centres and services, especially those with severe disabilities, who are most vulnerable to social isolation and exclusion.

5.4 Summary

Policy priorities should be set that address gender differences between women's and men's educational access and usage. To begin with, undertake a mapping of existing national strategies, policies, and interventions for women. A first step in the diagnostic and analysis is to identify how education aligns with existing national policies, programs, and priorities. This may include a national inclusion policy targeting women.

Identify key stakeholder groups that work with women. The participation of different stakeholders representing the public and private sectors and civil society that target women must be secured. Women should be integrated into key stakeholder groups, so they have a voice in the decision-making process which further ensures the education program is grounded in the realities of key challenges. This may be achieved through the formation of an education working group for women that integrates key stakeholders representing a range of sectors.

Women are not a homogenous group and should be identified into different sub-groups to ensure the program is relevant to their varying preferences and education needs. Leveraging existing infrastructure, such as women's groups and networks can increase their participation and motivation. It is important to build the capacity of female trainers or teachers in both education content and through interactive, experiential methodologies appropriate to the different sub-groups of women. In addition to traditional education stakeholders, two important ways to adopt a community-wide approach include developing partnerships with community organisations and religious institutions that target women and gaining the support of women such as spouses, other family members and community leaders. It is equally important to identify ways in which men can be included and brought into the discussions to become allies.

Design well-defined education interventions for women through efficient, appropriate and innovative mix of face-to-face and virtual delivery channels by aligning education activities with the needs and demands of women. The distance to the learning venue also needs to be considered as most women are not keen to travel long distances to receive training. Offering childcare and flexible hours to take part will encourage more consistent participation of women in educational activities, and it may also be necessary to offer alternative methods to access the content.

To conclude, the following policy recommendations should be considered for each vulnerable group or segment: a) identify and prioritise target groups taking a nuanced approach towards understanding their specific education needs and learning preferences; b) Identify key stakeholders that work with the target group, integrate the target group into key stakeholder groups and adopt a community-wide approach; c) customise programs, build capacity of trainers or teachers, leverage existing touchpoints, teachable moments, and existing groups and networks for the target groups, and d) to see what of impact on vulnerable groups, conduct monitoring and evaluation of these targeted education programs. Building on the above policy considerations, specific vulnerable groups can be integrated in every stage of an existing or new policy formulation, implementation, monitoring, and evaluation.

There is a clear lack of data on Syrian women refugees in Lebanon. It is very important to conduct further needs assessments that should focus on groups such as women's spouses, community leaders, local community-based women groups, and religious based organisations to clarify the risks that vulnerable women face. In other words, understanding the ways that vulnerable women's health, mental and social problems differ from local Lebanese counterparts.

Many Syrian vulnerable women are reluctant to speak about their issues mainly due to patriarchal and cultural elements. A thorough needs assessment is a good place to start to understand the landscape of Syrian women's and other vulnerable groups' needs. In this regard, one policy recommendation should aim at providing a medium that would allow vulnerable women more control or autonomy over their lives.

A policy recommendation is to coordinate with international agencies to facilitate flexible regulations allowing vulnerable young people without a residence permit to sit for Lebanese official exams and enrol in schools. In addition, priority should also be placed to allow such vulnerable young people access technical and vocational training linked to job opportunities. Key target groups such as young people with representation from different sub-segments and young influencers (e.g., parents, caregivers, and teachers) should also be involved.

After eleven years of dealing with the refugee crisis, Lebanon does not have a clear national strategy to systematically and efficiently respond to it. In effect, the municipalities have had shouldered such a burden given the insufficiency of aid that can be attributed to donor fatigue. It is recommended that an official communication channel should be established between the Lebanese national government and the local authorities to respond to the crisis. Therefore,

more standardised responses should be left to the municipalities in charge of absorbing and caring for refugees and other vulnerable groups, providing them with basic needs. As international agencies and donors realise the importance of municipalities as authoritative local bodies and provide them with more support, management would improve and tensions between host populations and vulnerable groups would be reduced.

To ensure that community-based support mechanisms are strengthened to address the social and psychological needs of vulnerable groups, it is recommended that a policy is set to explore resources and mechanisms which can be used to deal with psychosocial issues affecting the well-being of vulnerable groups of concern. Such a policy should be geared at facilitating discussion on sensitive subjects, increase participation of marginalised groups, counter stigma, and discrimination, and reduce risks of sexual and gender-based violence and other forms of abuse. It is further recommended that such a policy ought to make provision for reporting and accountability to vulnerable groups in the areas of: communication and transparency, participation and inclusion, feedback and response mechanisms, and program adaptation and learning.

Another policy recommendation is to engage international stakeholders to put more emphasis on fostering social cohesion among refugees, vulnerable groups, and Lebanon as a host society to such groups, which means allocating more resources to counter disinformation about refugees and the manifestation of ill sentiments towards FDP. This would also require the pursuit of initiatives that support the Lebanese and vulnerable groups at the same time by placing particular emphasis on the good contributions that FDP can make to Lebanon as a host. Needless to say, incorporating local NGOs and relevant stakeholders into the design and planning phases of programs to ensure interventions are sensitive to local tensions.

6 Policy brief summarising the main results and findings of the project for stakeholders from Menedék (Hungary)

6.1 Vulnerability

Generally speaking, there is equality of rights at the level of the law, which means that FDP enjoy the same rights as Hungarian citizens⁷. At the same time, FDP must overcome obstacles to the exercise of their rights that a Hungarian national would not, such as lack of language skills, prejudices of the majority society and difficulties caused by cultural differences. Thus, equal rights in practice do not mean equal opportunities in education, employment or health care. It can also be said that some groups within the FDP are even more vulnerable. These vulnerabilities stem from the life situation of the individual, which the Hungarian social policy system not only fails to balance, but the inadequate existence or complete absence of integration support services (e.g., housing assistance or state-funded language courses) makes them even more vulnerable.

In addition to equal rights, FDP should be able to benefit from various targeted support services and benefits in order to achieve real equality of opportunity (positive discrimination).

6.1.1 On micro-level. Considerations about personal conditions and features

Individual factors:

There are individual qualities and characteristics that make individuals vulnerable in certain situations. In Hungary. Trauma survivors are particularly vulnerable in terms of mental health care because they do not have proper access to state mental health care. Legislation allows them to go to the local mental health services, but in practice there are few professionals and language accessibility is not addressed⁸. The role of NGOs in this area is enhanced, but for funding reasons it is unclear what capacity they have to provide help to those who seek it.

Emphasis should be placed on the availability of appropriate psychological services for traumatised FDP as well as language accessibility of services.

Intra-family factors:

The situation of FD women: Single-earner, patriarchal family model is typical among the FD families, the man works, and the woman runs the household⁹. Women's vulnerability is affected by the community acceptance of divorce itself or of living alone (not in her husband's or father's house). Employment rates are lower among women, and if they do work, it is mostly because of economic (not being able to survive as a single-earner family) or independence pressures (leaving an abusive relationship). It is common for them to be able to work only part-time in addition to child-rearing and domestic work. This leaves women in a more vulnerable economic position. When leaving an abusive relationship, FD women have the same rights and support opportunities as Hungarians¹⁰. At the same time,

⁷ Act LXXX of 2007, § 10 (1)

⁸ Act CLIV of 1997, § 3 (s)

⁹ Sos, S., (2021). Resources and strategies for the successful social integration of muslim women granted international protection in Hungary, Social integration of beneficiaries of international protection in Hungary – NIEM policy briefs, Menedék Association.

¹⁰ Act LXXX of 2007, § 10 (1)

the specialised state institutions are saturated and are not ready to receive women who do not speak Hungarian and come from different cultural backgrounds. Such shelters are designed to be located very far from the place of residence, but this is also a barrier for FD women. This is because they are already somewhat settled in their place of residence, and it is difficult to start again in an unfamiliar place. This is why it would be important to support FD women who are single mothers or about to leave an abusive relationship with housing start-up support to help them restart their lives, while putting a great emphasis on their ethnical and cultural backgrounds and surroundings. In many cases, being in the household also leads to social isolation, so there is not a trusting, supportive safety net around them. In the absence of Hungarian language skills or at least English language knowledge, they find it difficult to integrate into the mainstream society. In order to reduce social isolation, it would be necessary to organise more community programmes targeting housekeeper women. These could include language learning, integration events and skills development, as well as leisure activities with the majority society. Women without children find it more difficult to leave an abusive relationship and move into shelter than those who have children. This is because the institutional system favours women with children.

Only religious marriage is common among FDP's country of origin and divorce is only a religious divorce. During the asylum interview, the religious marriage is recognised as a civil marriage, but in practice, if a divorce is granted, it is a religious divorce, not a civil one. This also means that the FD women are listed as married in the Hungarian state system, so their access to single parent benefits is questionable. Furthermore, if the woman's protection status is linked to her husband's persecution, this may also be at risk in the event of divorce¹¹. The Hungarian government does not intend to ratify the Istanbul Convention, citing gender theory and anti-migration arguments (Palfi, 2020). For the last 10 years, the government has been using a strategy of enemy image in public policy discourse, including migrants and gender theory. It would be important to transpose the Istanbul Convention into the Hungarian legal environment. This would help to ensure that the refugee status of abused women whose status depends on their husband's status can be maintained in the event of a divorce. Also support programmes for women should be set up to inform them about their rights.

Community factors:

Since 2015, the Hungarian government has been running anti-refugee and anti-migrant propaganda. As a result, xenophobia and Islamophobia have increased in the country¹². However, the individual experiences of those affected may differ¹³. There is a fundamental lack of state integration programmes and mechanisms. Since 2020, it is not even possible to apply for asylum in the country without a positive assessment of a letter of intent submitted to the embassy in Kiev or Belgrade. It should be possible again to apply for asylum in the territory of the country if someone is already staying here. During the asylum procedure and for one month after recognition, it is possible to stay in a reception centre where the state does not provide any services other than the preparation of basic needs and documentation. Language courses, housing, job search, schooling, etc. are the responsibility of the NGOs¹⁴. The state should organise integration programs at the reception centres, such as Hungarian language courses, support to find long-term housing, job clubs and leisure activities. Not all reception centres are in suitable locations, some are far

¹¹ from an ARU member

¹² Németh, A., (2021). Changes in social attitudes towards refugees in Hungary, Social integration of beneficiaries of international protection in Hungary – NIEM policy briefs, Menedék Association

¹³ Szabó, A., (2016). A menekültek és oltalmazottak integrációjára vonatkozó nyári jogszabályváltozásokról, Fundamentum 20./ 2-4. p107-112. <https://abcug.hu/egy-kicsit-sem-erdekli-a-kormanyt-mi-lesz-a-befogadott-menekultekkel/>

¹⁴ https://infovilag.hu/magyartanitas_onkentesen_segitseg_menede/

away from the city, which makes initial integration quite difficult. Here, there is a bus service 1-2 times a week, but the FDP can only reach the city on their own if they pay their travel costs. Free, local public transportation should be available in the interest of the people's integration in between the reception centre and the city nearby. Families can turn to the local family and child welfare services, but most of the staff are not professionally prepared to support families with linguistic and cultural differences. They have no interpreting resources and many of the professionals who help them are not familiar with the specific rules for FDP. State financed translators should be available in all state service providers and migrant specific trainings should be provided for those social specialists who work with FDP. The state social policy basically supports families with children and with declared employment, and beneficiaries of international protection status can apply for these financial contributions, such as tax refunds and family tax allowances. The Family Home Building Allowance is a state subsidy for buying or building a home but is not available to beneficiaries of international protection. The personal scope of this law should be extended to allow refugees with a stable income who are already living in the country for a long period of time to benefit from this type of housing support. Single people or childless couples are particularly vulnerable, as are those who work undeclared¹⁵. FDP are more likely to be connected to their own ethnic communities in Hungary.

6.1.2 On meso-level. Interrelationships in the environments in Hungary

Economics factors:

Hungary is a transit country for migration, and disparities are growing within Hungarian society, with more and more people becoming poor¹⁶. FDP arriving in Hungary belong to the poorer strata of society in the first period due to the lack of social and integration support. In the absence of language skills, even if they are educated, they can only do unskilled, manual work such as cleaning, kitchen help, construction work. Many employers cannot employ someone in a skilled position who can only communicate in English and cannot speak Hungarian. You can only get a job in an international company if you speak English (or French), but you need to have a certificate of qualification for that. Language and vocational training for refugees should be provided to reduce labour market marginalisation. Many people are employed in the ethnic economy, typically in the hospitality industry. On the one hand, this is positive because it reinforces identity and the preservation of one's own culture, but on the other hand it generates social exclusion. At the same time, the hospitality sector is characterised by black or grey employment, which has a significant impact on long-term future planning. Even if they earn well in these jobs at the time, if they lose their job due to any external factor (e.g., Covid-19), they will not have access to the minimum social supports¹⁷. Furthermore, one of the basic requirements for applying citizenship is the proof of taxation on earned income. Basically, declared wages are low, but the cost of living and housing is high, which also leads to livelihood insecurity¹⁸. There should be state programs to create inclusive workplaces. The government should give extra support and tax discounts to those employers who employ FDP. This would help to increase the number of refugees in declared employment. Among FDP the single-earner family model is more common in the country of origin. In Hungary, the two-earner family model is the basis for a secure livelihood. This transition may take longer for families and be driven by an economic pressure.

¹⁵ http://real.mtak.hu/84679/1/MT_szikra_tavolodas_az_europai.pdf

http://real.mtak.hu/84674/1/Szikra_Dorottya_szelenyi_u.pdf

¹⁶ <https://mfor.hu/cikkek/makro/melyulo-szegenyseg-havi-67-ezer-forintbol-elnek-a-szegenyek-magyarorszagon.html>

¹⁷ https://nepszava.hu/3113937_meg-mindig-megeri-a-feketefoglalkoztatasi

¹⁸ Budai, B., (2021). Effect of the covid-19 pandemic on the labour market situation of beneficiaries of international protection in Hungary, Social integration of beneficiaries of international protection in Hungary – NIEM policy briefs, Menedék Association

Educational factors:

In Hungary, children between the ages of 3 and 16 are of compulsory school age. This means that the school or kindergarten in the district where you live must provide admission. This is provided for children living with their families with an international protection status. Asylum seeker children are also entitled to enrol in education, but this is not done because of administrative reasons. In some cases, it is done, but these are also initiated under external pressure (UNHCR, NGOs). In these cases, however, the children are not enrolled in the normal school system, but only in special language training sessions run by travelling teachers or the staff of the local family support services. A state school catch-up programme should be in place with the aim of developing the language and basic skills of asylum-seeking children and preparing them for entry into the normal school system. Schools do not receive extra professional and financial support from the state. There are differences between institutions - some ask for professional help from various NGOs and school district offices, others refuse to accept FD children altogether. Teachers of Hungarian as a foreign language work sporadically in the schools, but there are no extra support teachers regularly present with the FD children. In public school's class, sizes range from 25-30 pupils, so there is little individual attention to the special needs of FD children. Communication between teachers and parents is not smooth because of language barriers. It depends on the teacher's openness and flexibility in how this can be managed, and NGOs are also trying to contribute. A teacher of Hungarian as a foreign language should be available in every school where FD children are enrolled. Also, migrant specific trainings and counselling sessions with an intercultural expert should be available for the public schools for free.

The enrolment of children over the age of 16 is very difficult, it depends entirely on the school principal's discretionary decision. Practice shows that, without a good knowledge of Hungarian, enrolling over 16 years of age children is impossible¹⁹. There is only one school in Hungary who enrol FD children over 16.

If the FDP has not attended school in his/her country of origin or cannot provide documentary proof, the school management is entitled to decide which class to admit him/her to. It is common practice that children are not admitted to the class of their age but to a lower class. If a teaching assistant who speaks both the child's language and Hungarian were with the children in every class during the first period of schooling, this would help the child to catch up more easily. This would avoid placing the child in a class much lower than what corresponds to his/her age. There are some primary schools in the capital with a higher proportion of FD children, so they have some experience in educating FD children and have developed good practices. But for the leaders of other schools, this is an unknown and daunting terrain. In such cases, the higher level - the school district office - and the involvement of NGOs have a big role to play in finding appropriate solutions²⁰. In the area of access to education, unaccompanied minors (UAMs) are particularly vulnerable. Education for UAMs under the age of 16 is not practically available, although they are legally required to attend school as asylum seekers. The district schools of the children's home have so far refused to admit them. Previous practice was to transfer UAMs to primary school in another town. Generally speaking, UAMs who are already asylum seekers spend up to six months in Hungary without attending school. This pattern and the unlawful behaviour of the local school should be stopped as soon as possible. UAMs under the age of 16 need to be enrolled as soon as possible because being in peer community would stabilise their mental health and promote their personal development. Nevertheless, they are not allowed to go to school during the period of non-submission of

¹⁹ from an ARU member

²⁰ Bognár, K., Hetzer, K., (2021). Methodology for the integration of beneficiaries of international protection in Hungarian public education, Social integration of beneficiaries of international protection in Hungary – NIEM policy briefs, Menedék Association

the letter of intent. Legally they can only enrol to school after they have submitted their asylum application, which in practice can mean several months²¹. For FDP adults and children over 16 years old, three schools in the capital offer classes in primary and vocational education. These schools targeted mainly Hungarian adults, but due to the low interest of the local population, they are also open to FDP and it creates a kind of natural segregation. In one of these schools there is training specifically aimed at developing Hungarian language skills. In practice, it can be seen that the adults have to work in order to earn a living, so they are unable to attend these classes on daily basis. The young FDP living in the after-care system²² are forced to enter these schools, because of the Child Protection Act, they are obliged to continue their education to secure their housing. But usually, they do not attend the classes because they need to work to finance their own and their families' livelihoods in their country of origin. Scholarships should be funded for adult and youngsters living in after-care system, so they could study and earn money too.

In practice, the integration of FDP into university education is not solved²³. In order to be admitted to a university course in Hungarian, one's language competence must be very advanced, and one must graduate from the Hungarian school system. The university educations in English language are fee-based. University admission is based on secondary school graduation scores. The admission of a FDP who has started the university studies in the country of origin is entirely at the discretion of the management of the university (whether previous school documentary can or not provided), as is the waiving of tuition fees. There should be a universal system with special requirements for FDP when they are applying for university studies, so they would have chance to being admitted even for the courses in English without a tuition fee. The Central European University offers training for FDP, but it is more like a preparatory, orientation course²⁴. The state does not provide Hungarian language courses at all, this is done by NGOs with their own funding and limited capacity. Recognition of diplomas is a costly and complicated process, so FDP prefer not to get started²⁵. For this reason, the recognition of diplomas should be free of charge for beneficiaries of international protection. In the baccalaureate, migrants have the option to take an exam in Hungarian as a foreign language instead of Hungarian grammar and literature - this can be a good thing, but it is a disadvantage for specific further studies.

Socio-sanitary factors:

Asylum seekers and beneficiaries of international protection status are entitled to vaccination, emergency care and health screening examinations. But there are differences in specialised health care services available based on type of the international protection²⁶. Access to health care for UAMs is problematic. They only become fully eligible for full health care if they are asylum seekers, but to become that they need to submit a declaration of intent. In practice, this can take several months, thus excluding them from eligibility for non-emergency health care. Free and universal health care should be provided for UAMs already living in a children's home regardless of their status of the asylum

²¹ from an ARU member

²² In Hungary the unaccompanied minors live in the public child protection system. The after-care system is part of it for children in between 18-24 year old.

²³ Lakatos, Zs., Faludi, J., (2021). Opportunities for supporting higher educational studies of beneficiaries of international protection in Hungary, Social integration of beneficiaries of international protection in Hungary – NIEM policy briefs, Menedék Association

²⁴ <https://olive.ceu.edu/about-olive>

²⁵ from an ARU member

²⁶ Tóth, J., (2021). Access to healthcare for beneficiaries of international protection in Hungary – analysis and recommendations, Social integration of beneficiaries of international protection in Hungary – NIEM policy briefs, Menedék Association

procedure. Children receive mandatory vaccinations and booster shots. Health care is available to beneficiaries of international protection in the same way as it is for a Hungarian citizen if they pay the social security contribution. For the first 6 months after recognition, health care is available without paying a fee. Communication between doctor and patient is difficult due to language barriers. State financed translators should be available in the health care service providers. No emphasis is placed on mental health maintenance and trauma counselling. There should be interculturally trained and trauma-informed psychological support available for FDP. There is no permanent medical or health staff in the reception centres. At least nurses should be available at the reception centres or drivers, who can take the person with a health problem to the nearest hospital.

Labour factors:

Beneficiaries of international protection can work under the same conditions as Hungarian citizens, so there is no administrative obstacle. But there is no public employment policy specifically targeting FDP. They can be involved in public employment, which has the principle aims at integration into the labour market, but in reality, is a work for below-market wages. Asylum seekers can only be employed if their application has not been assessed for 9 months, but even then, they can only be employed with a work permit or in public employment. This process takes 70 days, but in practice temporary residence permits for asylum seekers are granted for less than this. Legislation and deadlines should be harmonised to ensure that asylum seekers have a realistic chance of employment. Many FDP works in the ethnic economy, which leads to social isolation from the majority society. The integration of women into the labour market is more difficult, especially if they have children, as in Hungary part-time employment is rare. The lack of Hungarian language skills and education only enable them to find employment in areas where working hours are not fixed, including weekend and evening working hours. Thus, they are often unable to do so because of the responsibility of looking after children²⁷. The government should promote part-time employment with labour market benefits or tax discounts, so this type of employment would be in the interest of employers.

6.1.3 On macro-level: macro-policies, culture, economic issues, believes, etc.

The Covid-19 pandemic has also negatively affected FDP, as they work in the hospitality industry in large numbers, and these places have closed, causing them to lose their jobs. They were not supported by the minimum social safety net, due to the undeclared work specific to the sector. During unemployment, they had no health insurance and were not entitled to job-seeker's allowance because of the previous undeclared employment. Those who did work declared and claimed unemployment benefit also received it months later because of the overburdened system²⁸. The pandemic has increased the number of people working as couriers and including many FDP, but in these food-delivery companies, the couriers are self-employed. This can also lead to vulnerability²⁹.

Since 2015, the government has been engaged in a strong anti-refugee, anti-migrant communication. The impact of this can be felt in the way mainstream care systems and institutions operate. It also shapes the attitude of the majority society towards FDP, which in turn makes it more difficult for refugees to integrate into the labour market

²⁷ Nagy-Nádasdi, A., R., (2021). Vulnerability and discrimination in employment of beneficiaries of international protection in Hungary, Social integration of beneficiaries of international protection in Hungary – NIEM policy briefs, Menedék Association
²⁸ Budai, B., (2021). Effect of the covid-19 pandemic on the labour market situation of beneficiaries of international protection in Hungary, Social integration of beneficiaries of international protection in Hungary – NIEM policy briefs, Menedék Association
²⁹ from an ARU member

and to rent housing³⁰. There should be social awareness-raising and awareness programmes among the majority population, so they became more open to FDP, thus help their integration.

6.2 People fleeing Ukraine in 2022

The legal environment for FDP from Ukraine is constantly changing. The information here reflects the current situation on 26.03.2022.

Ukrainian citizens, their third-country national family members, and people recognised with beneficiaries of international protection and their family members arriving after 24 of February from Ukraine may apply for temporary protection status in Hungary. Under current legislation, temporary protection status lasts until 1st of June³¹. In the meantime, the European Union has ruled that temporary protection status must be valid for one year, until March 2023, but the Hungarian government has not yet changed its regulation. It also means that third-country nationals with a valid residence permit from Ukraine cannot apply for temporary protection status in Hungary. An amendment to the regulation is needed to ensure that the temporary protection status is still valid after 1 June and that third-country nationals fleeing from Ukraine can also apply for temporary protection in Hungary.

Regarding the accommodation of applicant and beneficiaries of temporary protection is provided by the National Disaster Management Service, although no information is given in advance as to where. Practical experience shows that people are accommodated in hotels, summer camps and similar accommodation throughout the country. The Immigration Office and the National Disaster Management Service should work with the many NGOs to successfully support refugees from Ukraine. Applicants and beneficiaries of temporary protection are entitled to health care services and the children of compulsory school age can enrol in public schools. The applicants and beneficiaries of temporary protection are entitled to a monthly cash allowance but are also obliged to cooperate with the local Employment Office. If they do not accept the job offer, they will lose the cash allowance. In practice, it is not clear for applicants where and how they can apply for this support. They can be employed with a simplified work permit. According to the legislation, the state provides Hungarian language courses for asylum seekers, but this has not yet been put into practice³².

6.3 Issues of diversity

The Hungarian policy and care system is characterised by homogeneity and monoculturalism. Therefore, institutions have limited capacity to respond to and accommodate diversity in practice. Basically, institutions with different public functions (educational institutions, family services, health care workers) are dealing with staff shortages and overload. They are not able to respond adequately to the needs of FDP with special needs and they have lack knowledge of the specific legislation applicable to FDP. Language accessibility is not addressed at all within state institutions, where few professionals speak English, let alone the mother tongue of the FDP. In general, FDP face institutional discrimination due to the system's unpreparedness and ignorance. Employees of the state service providers should be trained to get specific skills how to work with VGs among FDP. Since 2019, the Office of the Commissioner for Fundamental Rights of Hungary (Ombudsman) has not really acted to investigate systemic violations of the law. This includes the fact that in cases of rejection of applications for Hungarian citizenship, there

³⁰ from an ARU member

³¹ 86/2022. (III. 7.) Government Decree

³² <https://menedek.hu/en/news/what-will-happen-people-fleeing-ukraine-last-update-09032022>
https://helsinki.hu/wp-content/uploads/2022/02/HHC_Ukraine_Guide_2022_03_09_EN.pdf

is no possibility to know the reason for the rejection. This used to be investigated by the Ombudsman Office, but in recent years it has not done so either³³. There should be a mandatory obligation to state reasons in the event of a naturalisation application being rejected, and a statutory time limit for the procedure.

6.4 Successful practices

Meso level: regular supervision sessions or case discussion sessions for support professionals working in NGOs, which develop professionals' self-awareness and self-reflection. Regular meetings for people working in different areas of the asylum field to be able to meet and to connect, to work together and build trust. It also makes the assistance to FDP more coordinated and effective. Concrete examples: Menedék Association had trainings for law enforcement officers, migrant specific training for social workers, children's rights training and case discussion sessions, teachers' network, ARU meetings, self-reflection case diaries for social workers.

Training for refugees:

- Hungarian language courses
 - State language course 1998-2013, 520 hours³⁴.
 - Hungarian language course at the Balassi Institute.
 - Menedék Association, Kalunba, Jesuit Refugee Service language learning programmes for adults and children.
- Vocational and integration training:
 - MMIA 2006-2016 training programmes: Nursery training, Digital Carrier Mapping
 - Menedék Association business start-up workshops, job search clubs held jointly with the local Employment Centre, which provide information on the labour market and develop other soft skills³⁵.
 - Artemisszió NGO training courses: <http://artemisszio.hu/running-projects>
 - CEU OLIVE programme: <https://olive.ceu.edu/about-olive>

State integration grants: before 2014 there were various integration grants, 6+6 months housing in a reception centre, supported housing, after 2014 this changed but still existed, since 2016 there is nothing³⁶.

Organising local community programmes for integration, where members of the migrant community and members of the majority society can meet to break down prejudices. An example is the Women's Club of the Menedék Association in cooperation with the local municipality³⁷. Various social awareness-raising events are held, for example in schools, by the Menedék Association and the Jesuit Refugee Service³⁸.

In the field of health, Refugee Health Procedure Protocol³⁹.

³³ <https://ataszjelenti.444.hu/2022/03/23/elvegzi-e-az-ombudsman-valaha-a-munkajat>

³⁴ http://ias.jak.ppke.hu/hir/ias/20183sz/06_SzepA_IAS_2018_3.pdf

³⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/employment_social/ECDB/equal/jsp/dpComplete_1135.htm
<https://adoc.pub/munkaer-piaci-orientacio-menedekkerknek.html>

³⁶ http://ias.jak.ppke.hu/hir/ias/20183sz/06_SzepA_IAS_2018_3.pdf

³⁷ <https://iozsefvaros.hu/egyetemvaros/76851/egy-konyha-harom-etel-hat-nemzet>

³⁸ <http://jmsz.hu/egyeb/felhivas-kozepiskolak-szamar/>

³⁹ Tóth, J., (2021). Access to healthcare for beneficiaries of international protection in Hungary – analysis and recommendations, Social integration of beneficiaries of international protection in Hungary – NIEM policy briefs, Menedék Association

6.5 Summary

In general, among FDP, women and unaccompanied minors, as well as those in aftercare, are the most vulnerable. FDP are disadvantaged in all aspects of life due to a lack of language skills and Hungarian language learning programmes. This affects access to corresponding education, declared employment and access to healthcare. Vulnerable, traumatised refugees lack access to adequate psychological support services. Over the years, the Hungarian government has dismantled the asylum system, and asylum applications can no longer be lodged in the territory of the country. Thus, the situation for the care of refugees fleeing from Ukraine is also chaotic. Attitudes in the majority society have been significantly shaped by the anti-migrant propaganda that the government has been building up for years.

Chapter 6 of Hungary's Migration Strategy 2013-2020 deals with the integration strategy for migrants, including FDP⁴⁰. However, apart from laying down the theoretical foundations, it has not been implemented in practice. This strategy contains concrete proposals covering all areas of integration.

The objectives also include strategic points along the following policy units: comprehensive integration strategy, public education, higher education, labour market, vocational training, housing, political activity, inclusive society, UAMs, and young people living in the after-care system as a specific target group.

Among other recommendations from the Hungarian experience are language teaching for FDP, programmes to help children integrate into nursery and school, labour market integration, programmes to support the acquisition of vocational qualifications, supported housing, access to health and family support services, protection of UAMs and young people living in after-care system, the address of a responsible ministry, the setting up of a consultative forum bringing together governmental and non-governmental organisations.

The main recommendation would be to translate the Migration Strategy into practical implementation, as these are complex proposals that affect all aspects of FDP's integration.

⁴⁰ http://belugyalapok.hu/alapok/sites/default/files/MMIA_.pdf

7 Policy brief summarising the main results and findings of the project for stakeholders from Yarmouk University (Jordan)

7.1 Vulnerability

7.1.1 On micro-level. Considerations about personal conditions and features

In Jordan context, the team focuses on psychological support factors that considered the complex interplay between individuals, families' relationships, and communities' factors. Psychological support allows to understand the range of these factors that put the VGs in Jordan at risk for violence or protect them from experiencing perpetrating violence.

In individual level factors, the team identified the biological and personal history factors that increase the likelihood of becoming a victim or perpetrator of violence. These factors were identified to reduce Gender-Based Violence (GBV) through prevention and mitigation strategies in all areas of the humanitarian response in Jordan, such as age, education, income, substance use, or history of abuse, history of travel, medical history (mental health, trauma, disability, etc.) and others. Therefore, some of the proposed training programs included conflict resolution and life skills training, social-emotional learning, and safe dating and healthy relationship skill programs. In our approach, the training includes an introduction to these Guidelines and provides an overview of GBV, an explanation of why the considered violence is a source of protection concern for all humanitarian actors and lists several recommendations to ensure the implementation of these instructions.

The prevailing social and environmental pattern in Jordan suffers from several weaknesses extending from the displaced family and the vulnerable Jordanian families to the services provided by the country, which increased the exposure of family members to psychological violence as victims. Family members influence their behaviour and contribute to their experience. Prevention strategies at this level may include parenting or family-centred prevention programs and mentoring, and peer programs designed to strengthen parent-child communication, promote positive peer norms, problem-solving skills, and promote healthy relationships.

To strengthen the resilience of vulnerable groups, actors can act by promoting community inclusion and by providing access to direct care and support. In Jordan context, we identified community factors such as absence of social support, discrimination, where people live, learn, work, and play, addressing other conditions that give rise to violence in communities (e.g., neighbourhood poverty, residential segregation, instability, and high density). These factors include social and cultural norms in actors including health, economic, educational, and social policies that help maintain economic or social equality between groups in society. The most prominent examples of this are schools, workplaces, universities, and neighbourhoods, where social relationships arise from these places to avoid exposure to bullying and danger, which reduces the chances of community inclusion.

It is possible to assist refugees in getting rid of the psychological problems associated with their exposure to violence before asylum or during the asylum journey by raising their level of cognitive competence and introducing them to ways to obtain this type of care and specialised centres for this, and providing follow-up and full care for them until such type of problems are overcome.

7.1.2 On meso-level. Interrelationships in the environments in Jordan

Supporting local capacities to find solutions to the vulnerable groups in Jordan.

Economics factors:

The refugee in Jordan has the rights to enjoy a decent life through which he/she meets his/her nutritional, health and psychological needs. In addition, the refugee has to enjoy the needs for security that he/she could not obtain in the country of origin.

Refugees in Jordan are still exposed to many problems that require continuous support to be provided to empower them economically, and among the most prominent needs in this context are the need for food, finding a stable income and diversifying sources of aid, as there are many of them who are still not economically independent and have dependency on aid. Therefore, it is important to diversify the provision of assistance to them and not be satisfied just with food aid, so free training programs should be available that help the vulnerable to gain economic independence and qualify them to join some professions or practice handicrafts.

The host country should have policies that help them in marketing their products, so full information should be provided to VGs to help and develop themselves. In addition, it guides them to know the jobs available to them and the rights that limit their exploitation. This requires the development of special legislation for these groups in terms of facilitating the procedures for obtaining work permits and reducing fees for each permit obtained considering the recognition of the status of refugees in Jordan, the methods of applying for jobs, and setting the minimum wage.

It is also assumed that the provision of in-kind assistance to refugees will not stop except when ensuring that they obtain a stable monthly income as a result of joining some jobs, provided that this income is sufficient to achieve the requirements of a decent living in their capabilities.

In addition to this, it is assumed that special legislations for renting refugees should be developed, as there are prejudices among many real estate owners about renting them due to the presence of large numbers of refugees who live in the same rented housing. Some families resort to living in the same dwelling due to the lack of financial and economic possibilities to do it in other way, often exacerbated by problems of their families and economic empowerment. Therefore, the legislation may limit these problems and confirm the refugee's right to obtain suitable housing. The legislation may include the authorities concerned with paying the rent, especially because the reluctance of some owners is due to the refugees' inability to pay the rent.

Educational factors:

Undoubtedly, the difficult living conditions in Jordan and the overcrowding of educational classrooms limit the possibility of integrating displaced students together with Jordanian students. Therefore, evening schools have been allocated to teach refugee students, and this may deprive refugee students of the opportunity to integrate with Jordanian society. It is necessary to work on amending the rotational education policy in force in the Jordanian Ministry of Education so that Syrian students can integrate with Jordanian students and not be placed in private schools during the evening period. In addition, work must be done to prepare the infrastructure in schools and remote areas so that through this preparation, opportunities to benefit from distance learning are available, and work is supposed to create the financial capabilities that help young Syrian students and female students to reach schools. This is especially important since there is a reluctance among some refugee families to send their children to the school due to the financial cost of using transportation to reach school. Special legislations will be put in place for the enrolment of Syrian students after high school in universities, and the organisations that can work to finance students' studies in universities should be determined. Legislation may include setting tuition fees, treating refugees

as Jordanians in terms of fees, and working to reformulate legislation to allow students to benefit from student employment within universities, which is currently limited to Jordanian students.

Socio-sanitary factors:

Health and social practices in Jordan are an urgent need for all groups. It becomes more complicated when talking about displaced people due to their different priorities. Health and social care for refugees in Jordan may be available to a certain category of refugees, especially those who have knowledge and have the ability to move to benefit from health services; however, it is a problem for some refugees like the elderly, women and disadvantaged children, or those who do not have the financial means and do not know how to apply to health care, especially if refugees do not have refugee status in Jordan. Therefore, clear and specific legislation must be developed within action steps to help provide the possibilities for access to health care for all groups of refugees. It is also assumed that refugees are familiarised with the centres that care for them and provide a database to standardise the process of benefiting from these services and to prevent the recurrence of using services from more than one source. It is also necessary to provide legislation and centres concerned with providing health care services in the evening times, especially for refugees who do not have time to take care of their families or themselves because of some work, so that they can accompany their families or themselves after returning from work.

Moreover, refugees may engage in some work that lacks adequate health protection, and the presence of some families in remote areas may deprive them of the opportunity to obtain vaccinations for their children or medical and psychological treatment. Organisations and legislation are supposed to guarantee refugees opportunities to benefit from specialised doctors, as it is noted that there is a scarcity in the number of doctors working in the centres concerned with providing health care to refugees. In general, the number of doctors and workers who provide support to refugees must be increased. These must be trained to help refugees make better use of health care services. It is also needed to work on providing psychological care by providing a larger number of psychiatrists and providing a database that allows to identify each case and whether it benefits from psychological care services or not. In addition, training and preparation for specialists must be provided to become more efficient in providing psychological care from a multicultural perspective.

In addition, the health systems in the Jordanian community may be ill equipped to respond to the needs of the displaced. There is a problem with the refugee health insurance system. Most health insurance is limited to Jordanians and therefore may be more limited for the displaced and refugees. By examining the health problems among the refugees, it is noted that there are many problems that need periodic follow-up, including heart and blood vessel problems, pregnancy and childbirth problems, diabetes, and blood pressure.

Therefore, there is still an urgent need to work on creating preventive and curative programs through which to organise the health empowerment of refugees. In this way, they can become more aware of the nature of the problems and the procedures that are supposed to be followed when they face any of these problems. In addition, these programs familiarise them with the sources to obtain health services in an appropriate manner, which may reduce the problem of integration into society.

Labour factors:

There is no doubt that there are many problems that displaced people in Jordan face in local organisations. These problems vary between the exploitation and unemployment. The exploitation when they are in need to obtain money to meet the requirements of life, and unemployment in the event of non-acceptance of this exploitation.

Sometimes, the displaced refuse to work for long hours, low wages, hard work or unhealthy conditions. There are sometimes difficulties to obtain work permits, and the presence in some professions is limited to Jordanians, so the displaced cannot be integrated.

At the same time, the increase in the number of FDP in Jordan has increased pressure on Jordan's resources. This requires finding an integrated plan to deal with such issues and to enable the displaced to obtain opportunities to get appropriate jobs to achieve social justice with the members of Jordanian society. This may lead to enabling the displaced to rely on themselves in securing their needs, because maintaining the provision of aid is not considered a solution in light of the continuous renewal of the refugees' needs. Therefore, special legislation must be developed that determines the nature of the work available to refugees, whether they are registered on the lists of refugees or those who are not registered as refugees, and this is to prevent their exploitation. Empowering refugees from a legal and economic point of view and speeding up the procedures for their transactions should avoid this. It is also interesting creating a website linked to work centres through which jobs available to refugees are announced, and legislations through which a certain percentage of refugee workers are allocated, especially in investment and business cases whose owners are Syrians.

7.1.3 On macro-level: macro-policies, culture, economic issues, believes, etc.

Jordan has faced many waves of asylum seekers over the past decades, whether Palestinian, Iraqi, Syrian and other waves of asylum. This was accompanied by the amendment and development of many legislations in a way that preserves the rights of refugees, prevents their exploitation, and guarantees them a decent life. This will ensure job opportunities to achieve their best, if there are internal and external donors and there is a real will to amend legislation and laws. Therefore, it is necessary to put in place legislation that preserves the rights of refugees and prevents their exploitation on the pretext that their presence may be illegal at times, and activate laws and legislations that prevent their exploitation and prevent early marriage and encourage the right in education for refugees at all school levels.

The outbreak of the Covid-19 has greatly affected the refugees in Jordan, and as a result, many psychological disorders appeared among the displaced that prevented them from achieving high levels of empowerment and mental health. The pandemics caused new burdens to emerge and this has doubled refugees' problems, especially for women. Among these new problems are, for instance, the need for the Internet (which may not be available to displaced families in Jordan), digital illiteracy in many families, and following children through platforms. The procedures the different actors set up have not been adapted to take into account the absence of digital knowledge among the elderly or vulnerable groups and the side requirements and effects. This has increased the financial burden as a result of the work being stopped and the enforced displaced persons not receiving the wages that used to meet some of their needs. The suspension of some projects, grants, and activities, partially or completely, as a result of the pandemic, has affected the work of the displaced, and many of them lost their jobs, and some of them fell into financial problems, which led to an increase in pressure and psychological suffering on them. All this facilitated them to be exploited by some business owners. So, it is necessary to work to activate oversight over institutions and their employees and to punish those who practice practices that conflict with legislation and laws.

In general, there is also needed to work on combating rumours related to the status of refugees and the size of the grants offered to them, because this has created a trust gap between the refugees and the host governments. The refugees believe that the government is earning huge money coming from donors because of their presence in

Jordan. Then, refugees feel unjust, because the money that they claim the countries give to Jordan to support refugees does not reach them, and this is a fallacy. It is necessary to work on correcting the ideas associated with it.

The presence of the displaced in Jordanian society deprived them of forming a national identity. This helped the emergence of personal traits that neglect the foundations and principles of sound socialisation, and consequently the spread of behaviours that do not express citizenship, such as respect for self and others, honesty, and justice. Therefore, it is necessary to focus on the development of personal traits as an effective means to strengthen positive behaviour and reduce deviation. This is what the training programs offered to them in the context of the project sought to achieve, as the focus was on empowering the displaced in terms of psychological, family, health, legal and economic terms.

7.2 *Issues of diversity*

There is need to review the situation of two groups in Jordan. First, for elderly, there must be a review of requests for asylum or family unification, since there are many elderly people who do not have a breadwinner inside Jordan. This requires reconsidering visits or residence for those who are interested in providing care for them. Second, there is a need to consider study times for the vulnerable groups in schools. Actors need to provide the financial capabilities that help them to reach the school, so they stop being in danger of being prone to leave the school due to the difficulty of accessing it and the financial demands it sometimes requires.

Also, actors need to adopt specific programs to provide services to the displaced considering their age stages, disability, or other specific issues. They have to include issues and problems specific to each age group, as issues related to adolescents differ from those related to married people, and issues related to males may differ from those of females, and the issues of people with disabilities and their needs may differ from those of ordinary people. In addition, it must be noted that the issues and problems of these groups with the rest of the Jordanian society may differ from the nature of these problems between the displaced of different groups. It is also possible to recommend the necessity of training psychosocial care providers regarding the importance of cultural pluralism and being open to different cultures to be more effective in providing such services.

7.3 *Successful practices*

There are many successful practices regarding psychological and social support services to the displaced in Jordan. One of the best practices that can be developed to improve the integration strategy in Jordan is to support institutions that provide services to refugees, and to provide adequate training for their staff on special support programs and local and international legislation to deal with various issues.

There is also a need to provide local and international application, tools and standards that suit marginalised groups of Jordanians and vulnerable displaced, according to the available capabilities, and to encourage volunteer work according to the scientific method.

The stakeholders in Jordan could design training programs based on the results of the study carried out in the project and in line with the needs of these groups. The project team worked on training the providers of training programs (the trainers) on the mechanism of dealing with these groups (the displaced) considering cultural pluralism. The program relies on psychological and social support that reveals the differences between refugees in Jordan. This must ensure that the programs are implemented by specialists in each field, and evaluated after implementation according to local standards to ensure the dissemination of the programs. It should be noted that the design of the

programs relied on the content of international programs provided for this type of groups (displaced people) and worked to modify the contents of some activities in line with the prevailing culture and privacy among the displaced, and the integration of women was mainly considered to benefit from these programs.

7.4 Summary

It is noted that there are many children who are exploited in some work in the morning shifts because they do not enrol in schools with Jordanian students. Therefore, work must be done to get rid of the double-shift system and to integrate Syrian students with Jordanian students to unify their study times and control as much as possible over exploitation them and not go to study.

It is noted that there is a reluctance not to send students to schools, especially by families who live in remote places, and therefore it is necessary to work on developing legislation and providing transportation means that transport students to their schools and then return them home after completion.

It is noticed the absence of specialisation among the providers of psychological care for vulnerable groups, and therefore it is necessary to train the working groups and enable them to provide the basis for providing psychological and social support services, in addition to working on the development of legislation that defines the groups that are supposed to provide such services.

It is noted that training programs are generally provided to refugees without taking into account their needs and the extent of their access to the required care, so it is necessary to work on surveying the different needs of vulnerable groups, taking into account each of the different factors (gender, disability, sexual orientation, age, and ethnicity) through the application of tools measurement and tests prepared specifically for this category, and to verify the psychometric properties of these tools so that they are far from bias and as close as possible to objectivity.

It is noted that there are many psychological disorders and emotional problems that have not been effectively dealt with, and a great deal has been relied on pharmacological treatment and no focus on cognitive-behavioural therapy. The importance of activating cognitive behavioural therapy along with pharmacotherapy.

It is noted that there are many individuals who join modest wages to obtain a source of income that helps the individual himself and his family members. Therefore, it is necessary to activate oversight of employers and to intensify the penalties, as it has not been proven that he exploits refugees.

It is noted that some homeowners refrain from renting refugees, and therefore it is necessary to work on organizing the rental process and identifying concerned parties that follow up on the payment of wages, and legislations are put in place to determine the numbers that can live in the house if it is rented.

It is noted that there are specific programs concerned with specific age groups, and this may lead to the prohibition of other groups from benefiting from the programs according to their needs. Therefore, it is necessary to work on developing current programs for health, legal, psychological, family, and economic empowerment in line with the needs of vulnerable groups, considering the different factors (gender, disability, sexual orientation, age, and ethnicity) in the host country.

Training workers with vulnerable groups on various training programs to ensure that they possess knowledge and skill in the field of training, by providing them with an appropriate mechanism to deal with issues of cultural pluralism, to ensure greater effectiveness in implementing such programs.

The necessity of educating the various organisations and their employees on the importance of considering cultural pluralism that prevents mixing between the sexes, and through which the specificity of some problems of individuals of both sexes is considered.

Diversification of activities in training programs, so the predominant character becomes practical application and not theory.

Work on defining legal concepts so that there is a common ground in their interpretation between countries, and this eliminates the difference in viewpoints significantly.

It is assumed that there should be specific measures that help protect women who have been subjected to violence or rape.

Work should be done to train people on issues of cultural diversity, social diversity, and gender-based violence.

8 Conclusions

Although these Policy Recommendations (PRs) are subject to the idiosyncrasy of each partner country of the consortium (Turkey, Italy, Spain, Finland, Lebanon, Hungary, and Jordan), there are some PRs that are common to different geographical areas, revealing its paramount relevance. Among them, we must highlight the following ones:

- Employees and volunteers of service providers should be trained to get specific skills on how to work with HVGs among FDP, including training in gender perspective and issues of diversity.
- Ensuring adequate health care for FDP with a cross-cultural and gender-oriented approach, with a special focus on mental health and especially considering the specific needs of the HVGs groups among the FDP.
- Specific PRs have been collected referring to women FDP aimed at improving their empowerment, their economic independence and their health care: fight against gender violence and develop guidelines that reflect the diversity of gender-based violence; modify the Geneva Convention to expressly include persecution based on gender and age as grounds for asylum; address diversity within women FDP; establish clear protocols for the protection of refugee women who have suffered violence; equalise the representation and influence of women in community leadership and management structures; provide support to ease caretaking, and improve statistical information on women FDP to better address their diversity and needs assessment.
- Specific PRs have also been collected referring to other groups such as the LGBTQI+ community (e.g. specific resources, increase their employability and representation in public institutions and organisations), older people (e.g. right to a pension, and prevention of elder abuse), minors (e.g. protection from abuse and exploitation, guarantee special protection for unaccompanied minors), and people with disabilities (e.g. more targeted attention, community-based rehabilitation activities) among the FDP.
- The primary aim of reception should be inclusion and integration, not confinement and security. Creating networks for social cohesion between host society and FDP is recommended, as well as setting up support groups for HVGs among the FDP. For example, by facilitating the work of neighbourhood associations.
- Adapting policies and attention and inclusion strategies for FDP considering the specific needs and challenges of HVGs. With this aim, issues of diversity, such as race, gender, sexual identity and orientation, age, or disabilities must be considered. The duration of the social care and inclusion processes of VGs should be adapted to their greater needs.
- The notion of vulnerability needs to be seen as contextual and situational, depending on the personal situation, but also on the host community and on the interactions between these two factors. So, we must look beyond those traditionally defined as vulnerable groups and adapt the measures to the different vulnerability contexts that are configured in each place.
- Collaboration among the different stakeholders needs to be increased: international organisations, national governments, regional and local authorities, NGOs, trade associations, companies and small business, schools, etc.
- Promote an alliance among the Third Sector and other areas to manage diversity. More inspections and control mechanisms are needed to avoid discrimination.
- Some partners recommend the improvement of the existing country regulations; however, all partners urge to guarantee the implementation and supervision of the regulations that protect HVGs among the FDP.

- Specific measures are proposed to increase the employability of FDP: facilitating the procedures for obtaining work permits, improve the offer of vocational courses, tax deductions to employers employing FDP, developing a skills recognition system, promoting their access to more qualified jobs, allowing the compatibility of part-time jobs with social aid and subsidies, information campaigns between companies and workers about the situation of the FDP involving the trade unions, reserving a quota to hire for vulnerable groups among FDP.
- Specific measures are also proposed to improve education reducing social, economic, and cultural inequalities: facilitating the homologation of official educational certificates, management of multiculturalism also with migrant specific trainings and counselling sessions, an effective and efficient investment in education and training, more help with the language, curricular and other adaptations at university, developing language and basic skills of children FDP to prepare them for the normal school system, measures to reduce school dropout, and granting early childhood education for FDP.
- Impose sanctions to the media or organisations that generate or spread hate speech and fake news referring to FDP, especially in the case of HVGs such as unaccompanied minors.
- Apply specific measures aimed at solving the severe housing problem for the FDP.
- Include FDP in the design and planning process of attention and inclusion policies and practices, aiming at their full individual autonomy.
- Ensure that HVGs among the FDP are fully informed of their rights in a form and language they can effectively understand, including the consequences of seeking asylum in the first EU country they arrive in and being informed of the reasons if their asylum application is rejected.
- Guarantee the national uniformity of policies avoiding significant differences among regions within the same country.
- Regarding the recent conflict in Ukraine, European cooperation should remain flexible enough to respond to both current and future challenges. As the European Union has decided to streamline the asylum application processes for Ukrainian citizens, if more resources are not allocated, the slowdown in the migratory processes of the rest of the nationalities will give rise to many people suddenly finding themselves in an irregular situation, increasing their vulnerability. Proposals for more advantageous policies and practices are always welcome, but are insufficient if sufficient budgetary and human resources are not allocated.

In addition to the previously mentioned common points, we encourage a detailed reading of the contributions of each RAISD partner that specifies how these PRs could be implemented in each context. All the observations and suggestions that have been collected in this deliverable are valuable outputs obtained throughout RAISD project that should be considered by all stakeholders specialising in forced migration during health, social and international crisis such as pandemics, international conflicts, and the increasing polarisation of the public discourse.

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